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Ph.D. Thesis

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On determination of ignition delay times
for the modeling of DDT

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Streszczenie

Trójwymiarowa teoria detonacji nie została jeszcze opracowana, dlatego naukowcy i inżynierowie używają eksperymentalnych parametrów by opisać i skategoryzować dynamikę detonacji. Najczęściej wykorzystywane parametry to wielkość komórki detonacji, czas opóźnienia zapłonu, krytyczna energia zapłonu, krytyczna średnica rury detonacyjnej, itd. Potrzeba oceny skłonności do detonacji różnych mieszanin (detonacyjności) przyczyniła się do powstania fenomenologicznych korelacji pomiędzy tymi parametrami a parametrami, które mogą być obliczone z modelu ZND, czyli czasem opóźnienia zapłonu za wiodącą falą uderzeniową, szerokością strefy indukcji, szerokością strefy reakcji, itd. Jednak okazuje się, że te obliczone wartości zależą w bardzo dużym stopniu od użytego szczegółowego mechanizmu reakcji chemicznych. Przykładowo: w przypadku szerokości strefy indukcji w mieszaninie stechiometrycznej etanu i powietrza znacząco różniące się między sobą wartości: 1.9 mm, 1.0 mm i 0.85 mm otrzymuje się w wyniku obliczeń przy wykorzystaniu mechanizmów GRI-mech 3.0, Konnov 0.5 i Aramco 2.0. Sam czas opóźnienia zapłonu jest kluczowym parametrem kontrolującym przejście z deflagracji do detonacji i propagację detonacji. Dodatkowo, używany jest do pośredniego testowania mechanizmów.

W celu umożliwienia wiarygodnej analizy detonacyjności, obliczeń przejścia z deflagracji do detonacji i samej detonacji, przeprowadzono ocenę szczegółowych mechanizmów reakcji chemicznych do symulacji czasów opóźnienia zapłonu. Analiza dotyczyła węglowodorów C1–C4, które stanowią grupę powszechnie wykorzystywanych paliw i, ponadto, ich kinetyka chemiczna jest istotna dla większych węglowodorów łańcuchowych. Obszerny przegląd literatury został przeprowadzony w poszukiwaniu czasów opóźnienia zapłonu z rur uderzeniowych, ponieważ to stanowisko badawcze w największym stopniu odzwierciedla warunki panujące za falą detonacyjną. Zebrane czasy indukcji zostały zasymulowane

piętnastoma znanymi mechanizmami, których dokładność następnie została podsumowana i porównana. Autorka przedstawiła wyniki na trzech poziomach ogólności, tym samym postulując, który mechanizm jest najlepszy w zależności od analizowanych warunków. Wnioski znacząco się różniły w zależności od mieszaniny i warunków termodynamicznych. Zaproponowano nowe sposoby prezentacji takich wyników. Na wykresach pudełkowych podsumowano statystyczny rozkład błędu względem temperatury, ciśnienia i wskaźnika stechiometrii. Mapy cieplne błędu od temperatury i ciśnienia dostarczyły więcej informacji o dokładności mechanizmów i podkreśliły warunki, w których potrzebne jest ulepszenie mechanizmów.

Dodatkowo, Autorka zaproponowała modele czasów opóźnienia zapłonu dla węglowodorów C1–C4 z wykorzystaniem głębokich sieci neuronowych. Opracowano dwa modele: jeden dla mieszanin rozcieńczonych argonem, drugi dla mieszanin rozcieńczonych azotem. Zaproponowane modele były wysoce dokładne i porównywalne z najlepszymi mechanizmami oraz, co najważniejsze, nieporównywalnie szybsze. Tym samym modele mogą być wykorzystane do obliczeń CFD przejścia z deflagracji do detonacji oraz propagacji samej detonacji. Modele mogą być z łatwością aktualizowane o kolejne mieszaniny i warunki termodynamiczne, gdy takowe zostaną opublikowane.

Keywords: szczegółowy mechanizm reakcji chemicznych, przejście z deflagracji do detonacji, głębokie uczenie maszynowe, czas opóźnienia samozapłonu, walidacja

Abstract

A quantitative theory of three-dimensional detonations has not been yet developed, thereby researchers and engineers use experimental parameters to describe and categorize the dynamics of detonation. The experimental parameters usually taken into consideration are detonation cell size, ignition delay time, critical initiation energy, critical tube diameter, etc. The need of detonability estimation led to the formulation of correlations between these parameters and the ones which can be computed from ZND theory: ignition delay time behind the leading shock wave, induction zone length and reaction zone width. Nevertheless, these calculated parameters strongly differ depending on the detailed chemical reaction mechanism used. For example, in the case of induction zone length calculations in a stoichiometric ethane-air mixture with the use of GRI-mech 3.0, Konnov 0.5 and Aramco 2.0 noticeably different values of 1.9 mm, 1.0 mm and 0.85 mm, respectively, are produced. Ignition delay time itself is a key physical property controlling the transition to detonation and the propagation of detonation. Moreover, it is used for indirect mechanisms testing.

In order to enable more reliable numerical investigations of the transition to detonation and detonation itself, the analysis of detailed reaction mechanisms' performance in the reproduction of ignition delay times was carried out. The analysis was devoted to C1–C4 hydrocarbons, as they form a group of globally used fuels and, moreover, their chemistry is important for non-aromatic species at high temperatures. An extensive literature review was done in search of ignition delay times from shock tube experiments as they most closely represent the conditions which appear in detonation. The accumulated ignition delay times were simulated with fifteen well established kinetic mechanisms and then the performance of the mechanisms was compared. The Author presented the comparison at

different levels of generality, hence providing guidance as to which mechanism performs best across all investigated conditions, which differed strongly between mixtures. Newly developed techniques were used to assess the ignition delay time prediction capabilities of the detailed reaction mechanisms. Box-whisker plots summarized the statistical dispersion of the applied error function across pressure, temperature and equivalence ratio. Additional heat maps of the error function on pressure-temperature plots provide more insight into the performance of mechanisms and highlight areas of uncertainty and possible improvement.

Additionally, ignition delay time models based on a Deep Neural Network (DNN) were proposed. Two models were developed: one for argon diluted mixtures and a second for nitrogen. The DNN models were highly accurate, and comparable with the best mechanisms. And most importantly, Ignition Delay Time (IDT) computations using the DNN models were incomparably much shorter than the best mechanisms. The developed models might be a reasonable choice for CFD simulations of deflagration to detonation transition. The models can be easily extended to new experimental data as published.

Keywords: detailed reaction mechanism, deflagration to detonation transition, deep learning, ignition delay time, validation

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Nomenclature

Variables

χ	stability parameter
Δ	induction zone length
δ	reaction zone width
γ	heat capacity ratio
λ	detonation cell width
ν	specific volume; stoichiometric coefficient
Φ	equivalence ratio
ρ	density
$\rho(x, y)$	Pearson coefficient between x and y
a	speed of sound
C	heat capacity
D	detonation velocity
E, erf	error function
E_a	activation energy
h	enthalpy
IDT, τ	ignition delay time
K	run-up distance parameter
k	rate coefficient
M	Mach number

P, p	pressure
Q, q	chemical energy
R	gas constant
r	rate of chemical reaction
Re	Reynolds number
S	flame speed
T	temperature
t	time
u	velocity
X	molar fraction
Y	molar fraction

Subscripts

0	reactants; initial state
1	products; initial state of test gas in shock tube
5	reflected shock wave condition
D	diluent
E, <i>exp</i>	experiment
P	constant pressure
PS	postshock state
S, <i>sim</i>	simulation
T	constant temperature
V	constant volume
vN	von Neumann condition (spike)

Chapter 1

Introduction

Chemistry of C1–C4 hydrocarbons plays an important role in the combustion of larger hydrocarbons. Alkenes are intermediate species and accurate prediction of their oxidation process has a major impact on hierarchical development of high-fidelity detailed reaction mechanisms. Sensitivity analyses with respect to reaction rate constants show that smaller species (C1–C4) chemistry is crucial for non-aromatic species at high temperatures when targeting flame speeds, species concentration profiles or ignition delay times [1]. Moreover, acetylene [2] and 1-alkenes [3] are precursors of soot and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) in fuel-rich conditions. Propene is a significant component of Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) [4, 5]. Iso-butene is a component of gasolines [6]. Hence, these alkenes and C1–C4 alkanes form a group of compounds of globally used fuels. Curran [1] notes that there is still a need for the community to develop and refine even these small mechanisms. One of the typical approaches for detailed reaction mechanisms' assessment is through indirect measurements. In this case a property of the whole combustion system is measured and key parameters are assessed, such as ignition delay time, laminar burning velocity and species' concentration profiles. Based on comparison of measurements and calculations with mechanisms, the mechanisms might be optimized to reach experimental values.

The ignition delay time value itself is important in process safety management. It controls the behavior of a detonation wave as well as detonation propensity of flammable mixtures. As a quantitative theory of three-dimensional detonation has not yet been developed [7], researchers and engineers use a number of experimental parameters to

describe and categorize the dynamics of detonation. Traditionally, mixture detonability is linked to detonation cell size and characteristic time scales (e.g., ignition delay time behind a leading shock wave). The need to estimate detonability led to the formulation of correlations between values which can be computed from ZND detonation theory [8–10] and experimental values. Nevertheless, the obtained values of detonation cell size, ignition delay time behind a leading shock wave or stability parameters can differ, strongly depending on the mechanism used. For example, in the case of induction zone length calculations in a stoichiometric ethane-air mixture with the use of GRI-mech 3.0 [11], Konnov 0.5 [12] and Aramco 2.0 [6, 13–18] noticeably different values of 1.9 mm, 1.0 mm and 0.85 mm, respectively, are produced. Wrongly calculated induction lengths lead to wrong values of detonation cell width, critical tube diameter, critical initiation energy, etc. Hence, selection of the appropriate chemical reaction mechanism becomes crucial.

The main motivation of this dissertation is to enable more reliable numerical investigations of deflagration to detonation transition. The first section of this research aims to provide more insight into performance of detailed reaction mechanisms in reproducing ignition delay times of C1–C4 hydrocarbons and to propose a method of robust presentation of obtained results. The goal is to deliver comprehensive, multidimensional analysis of the problem and to undertake discussion on statistical dispersion of results. In the second section, the goal is to develop an ignition delay time model based on an emerging technology, Deep Learning, and experimentally collected IDTs. Ideally, calculations with the model should be faster and as or more accurate than the *best* mechanism.

1.1 Detonation Theory

The first comprehensive study of gaseous detonation was conducted by Berthelot and Vieille [19] in 1881 in Paris, France. Their investigations of flame propagation in tubes showed that the detonations wave differs from other types of flame propagation. It travels with a constant supersonic speed of up to 2500 m/s, which depends on the mixture composition only and not on the tube diameter, if the diameter is not too small [20, 21]. At request of Ecole de Mines in Paris in order to mitigate firedamp explosion in mines, another pair of French researchers, Mallard and Chatelier [22] observed that the flame to detonation transition occurs rapidly, and that the detonation velocity is similar to the speed of sound in the burnt products [23].

This discovery initiated research in the field of explosions. Many independent studies on the first theory of detonation were conducted by Russian (Michelson [24]), English (Chapman [25], Dixon [26], Schuster [27]) and French (Jouguet [28], Crussard [29]) scientists. The detonation theory based on shock wave theory was first proposed by the Russian physicist Michelson [24] in 1893, however during this time Russian publications were unknown outside their country of origin [20] and the theory was named after Chapman [25] and Jouguet [28], becoming known as the CJ theory. In the CJ theory, the detonation wave is treated as a discontinuity, a shock wave with an infinite reaction rate and energy release inside the wave front, therefore no information regarding chemical kinetics of the mixture is needed. The conservation equations for mass, energy and momentum lead to a successful unique solution for the detonation velocity (CJ velocity).

Later, during World War II the CJ theory was refined independently by the Russian chemist Zel'dovich [8] in 1940, the Hungarian mathematician von Neumann [9] in 1942 in the United States and by the German theoretical physicist Döring [10] in 1943. Today, the proposed model is named after them, the ZND model. The ZND model provides the same detonation velocity as the CJ theory, with the only difference between two theories being the *thickness* of the wave. Refining the detonation wave and relaxing the assumption of infinite reaction rate leads to the process, where a shock wave transforms fresh mixture into post-shock condition (*von Neumann spike*) which lays on the unreacted Hugoniot curve. Then this ZND reaction zone goes to the CJ condition of fully reacted state by following the Rayleigh line [23]. Both the CJ theory and the ZND theory are macroscopic

models created for a one dimensional steady detonation wave in gaseous mixture. They do not explain the process of detonation initiation, its periodic cell structure, transverse waves or stability.

1.1.1 Chapman–Jouguet solution

Detonation is a combustion wave satisfying conservation equations of mass, momentum, and energy. The set of equations for a one dimensional steady flow across the combustion wave relative to the wave is as follows [7]:

Figure 1.1. A co-ordinate system fixed to the wave (the wave propagates in the rightward direction).

$$\rho_0 u_0 = \rho_1 u_1, \quad (1.1a)$$

$$p_0 + \rho_0 u_0^2 = p_1 + \rho_1 u_1^2, \quad (1.1b)$$

$$h_0 + q + \frac{u_0^2}{2} = h_1 + \frac{u_1^2}{2}. \quad (1.1c)$$

where the indices 0 and 1 mean reactants and products, respectively and q is the chemical energy released (the difference between the enthalpies of formation of reactants and products) not known initially, but to ease introduction to the detonation theory is assumed to be a constant. The enthalpies h_0 and h_1 are given by:

$$h = \frac{\gamma}{\gamma - 1} \frac{p}{\rho}. \quad (1.2)$$

Assuming that the initial state is specified (p_0, ρ_0, h_0), five parameters are unknown (p_1, ρ_1, u_1, h_1 and u_0) and there are four equations, therefore an additional equation is needed to solve the presented problem.

Hugoniot curve and Rayleigh line

Figure 1.2. The Hugoniot curve and Rayleigh line for a strong and weak solution (left) and for a CJ (tangent) solution (right). The point (1,1) indicates the initial state (the "0" state, the reactants). Reproduced from [7].

From Equations 1.1a and 1.1b the relation for the Rayleigh line can be derived. The Rayleigh line is a straight line when represented on a plot of $y = p_1/p_0$ against $x = \rho_0/\rho_1$ (e.g. Figure 1.2):

$$y = (1 + \gamma_0 M_0^2) - (\gamma_0 M_0^2)x, \quad (1.3)$$

and its slope $(-\gamma_0 M_0^2)$ is proportional to the square of the combustion wave speed:

$$\left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)_R = -\frac{y-1}{1-x}. \quad (1.4)$$

By combining the conservation equations the velocities in the energy conservation equation can be eliminated:

$$h_1 - (h_0 + q) = \frac{1}{2}(p_1 - p_0)(v_0 + v_1). \quad (1.5)$$

If a medium is assumed to be a perfect gas satisfying Equation 1.2, Equation 1.5 can be expressed as:

$$\left(y + \underbrace{\frac{\gamma_1 - 1}{\gamma_1 + 1}}_A\right) \left(x - \underbrace{\frac{\gamma_1 - 1}{\gamma_1 + 1}}_A\right) = \underbrace{\frac{\gamma_1 - 1}{\gamma_1 + 1} \left(\frac{\gamma_0 + 1}{\gamma_0 - 1} - \frac{\gamma_1 - 1}{\gamma_1 + 1} + 2q'\right)}_B. \quad (1.6)$$

Equation 1.6 in the form of $(y + A)(x - A) = B$ indicates that the Hugoniot curve has the shape of a rectangular hyperbola. Figure 1.2 (left) shows the Hugoniot curve and the Rayleigh line on $y = p_1/p_0$ against $x = \rho_0/\rho_1$ plot. The solution of the problem is the intersection of the Hugoniot curve with the Rayleigh line, as it must satisfy the conservation equations which are a base for both curves.

CJ solutions

The slope of the Hugoniot curve can be calculated as:

$$\left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)_H = -\frac{y + A}{x - A}. \quad (1.7)$$

In the points where the Rayleigh line is tangent to the Hugoniot curve two solutions are obtained, a detonation with minimum velocity and a deflagration with the highest velocity as showed in Figure 1.2 (right). These solutions are called the CJ solutions. Remarkably the upper solution (CJ detonation) has a very high level of agreement with experiments. The CJ solutions can be calculated by equating the slopes of the Rayleigh line, the Hugoniot curve and an isentrope in the detonation products ($p\nu^{\gamma_1} = \text{constant}$). The result is the flow Mach number downstream of a CJ detonation (or deflagration) equal to unity ($M_1^{CJ} = 1$). The detonation velocity with respect to a non-moving observer is then given by:

$$D = \sqrt{2((c_p/c_v)^2 - 1)Q} \quad (1.8)$$

In the case of a strong detonation the downstream flow is subsonic relative to the wave ($M_1 < 1$) and the downstream flow and the back boundary conditions can influence and disturb the combustion wave, i.e. expansion waves can penetrate the reaction zone and attenuate the wave. Hence, the strong detonations are not stable.

For the case of a weak detonation the downstream flow is supersonic and the downstream boundary conditions cannot disturb the combustion wave. It used to be arguable whether the weak detonation can exist and be stable in reality, however in 1942 von Neumann [9] showed geometrically that a mixture reacting progressively is described by a collection of Hugoniot curves (for each partially reacted state) and when these curves intersect one another in a particular way the Rayleigh line would intersect the

final equilibrium Hugoniot curve on the weak detonation location. In 1999 it was proven experimentally by Dionne et al. [30, 31] that a detonation wave speed in $\text{H}_2\text{-Cl}_2$ is higher than indicated by the CJ solution and the reason for that is an effectively higher energy release that drives the detonation above its equilibrium CJ velocity. To predict the velocity and analyze states of the pathological detonation a detailed kinetic study of the reaction zone structure has to be carried out.

1.1.2 ZND model

The ZND model scheme is presented in Figure 1.4. The model consists of the leading shock front, which adiabatically compresses gas from initial conditions (denoted with 0) to von Neumann conditions (von Neumann spike), where conditions are sufficient for a mixture to self-ignite. This is followed by the induction zone, where the gas starts to react, and then the reaction zone, where the rapid energy release takes place. The temperature increases across the detonation wave, firstly due to compression and secondly due to heat release from combustion to finally reach a CJ temperature. The pressure and density drop after compression due to expansion of the gas, which explains the acceleration of the gases backwards away from the front and which produces the forward thrust that supports the propagation of the leading shock wave.

Figure 1.3. ZND model of a detonation wave. Reproduced from [7].

The CJ solutions and the ZND structure can be calculated in Cantera utilizing the Shock & Detonation Toolbox written by Browne, Ziegler and Shepherd [32]. Selected algorithms for the numerical solution are described in the same reports [33, 34].

Figure 1.4. Temperature and pressure profiles calculated with SDToolbox and GRI-mech 3.0 mechanism for the ZND detonation of stoichiometric ambient methane–air mixture propagating with a CJ speed, 1802.8 m/s.

Figure 1.4 presents typical temperature and pressure profiles for a ZND detonation calculated with a detailed chemical kinetics mechanism, GRI-mech 3.0 [11]. Induction time and induction length behind the leading shock wave are 16.9 mm and 55.2 μs , respectively. These values differ strongly depending on the chemical reaction mechanism used, e.g.: 20.5 mm and 65.6 μs for CaltechMech [35–38], 24.2 mm and 79.2 μs for Polimi C1C3 LT HT 1412 [39] and 33.5 mm and 86.3 μs USC Mech II [40]. According to Lee [7] in case of inclusion of a single-step Arrhenius rate law, the most important parameter controlling the ZND structure is the activation energy, which is a measure of the temperature sensitivity of the chemical reaction. If the activation energy is high, the reaction progress is slow, the induction zone is long and the energy release is rapid. In case of the low activation energy the progress of the reaction is gradual. High activation energies cause instability of the ZND structure, however the instabilities cannot be resolved using a steady one-dimensional model. The detailed chemistry of the reactions plays an invaluable role in the detonation structure.

The analysis of the ZND detonation allows one to assess characteristic chemical length scales related to the detonation process, which further can be related with real detonation parameters.

1.1.3 Three-dimensional detonation

The first evidence that real detonations are unsteady and more complex than described by the CJ theory was given by Campbell and Woodhead [41, 42] in 1926 at the University of Manchester. They recorded a detonation in a 2CO-O_2 mixture saturated by water vapour using a rotating drum smear camera. They observed that the detonation wave rotates around the tube axis. They discovered spinning detonation. In 1959 in Moscow two students of Shchelkin: Denisov and Troshin [43], first reported on the discovery of the cellular (sometimes referred as the fish scale or diamond) structure of detonation waves using foils covered with a layer of soot. Four years later, Troshin and Shchelkin showed that the periodic cell structure is the result of hydrodynamic instabilities which generate transverse waves, later causing intermittent ignitions of the flammable gas [23].

In 1970 in his book *Introduction to Gasdynamics of Explosions* [44], Oppenheim described the detonation structure as an interaction of three shock waves - a stronger Mach stem, a weaker incident shock and to satisfy particle path direction, a reflected shock, as shown in Figure 1.5 (*top left*). A slip-line is a result of different routes and velocities of the gas particles traveling thru different shock waves. The shear in the slip-line eddies the flow behind the Mach stem. The point where three shocks intersect is able to write on the walls of the soot foils. Oppenheim described the cell structure as a living phenomenon, as the life span of each cell is short and undergo periodic cycles of decay and restoration.

Figure 1.5 presents cartoons by Oppenheim [44] from 1970 presenting flow of the gas particles and a soot foil, and a Schlieren photograph and a soot foil of a detonation in $\text{H}_2\text{-O}_2\text{-Ar}$ and $\text{H}_2\text{-N}_2\text{O-1.33N}_2$ taken by Austin and Shepherd in 2003 [45, 46]. The transverse waves and their role in detonation propagation were a subject of research by Pintgen, Austin and Shepherd from Caltech [45–47] and Teodorczyk, Radulescu and Lee [48, 49]. The group from Caltech observed that the transverse waves are the result of small, unstable amounts of released energy, and their contribution in sustaining a detonation is minimal. On the contrary, experiments performed in porous wall tubes by Teodorczyk and Lee [48], and later by Radulescu and Lee [49] showed that attenuation mechanism of detonations is by attenuation of the transverse waves. This is in agreement with Dupre et al. [50], who performed experiments in an acoustic absorbing walled tube, and Moen [51] summarised the mechanism as the tube walls act as reflective surfaces that maintain the

transverse waves. Pintgen et al. [47] noticed that their conclusions were made for diluted fuel-oxidizer mixtures, where Radulescu's experiments were made for mixtures without inert gas and with high activation energies.

The result of such complex three-dimensional structures is that both the CJ theory and the ZND model cannot accurately describe a real detonation. Lee in his book *The Detonation Phenomenon* [7] remarked that still "*the problem of reconciling the steady one-dimensional CJ theory with the transient three-dimensional structure of the detonation front remains unsolved to date*" (as of 2008).

1.1.4 Parameters of the gaseous detonations

As a quantitative theory of three dimensional detonation has not been yet developed, researchers and engineers use a few experimental parameters to describe and categorize the dynamics of the detonation. This categorization amounts to an assessment of detonation propensity (detonability) of different mixtures and is of great interest in industry due to safety reasons. The need of detonability estimation led to the formulation of correlations between values, which can be computed from the ZND theory and those experimental ones. These parameters are described in this subsection.

Detonation cell size

Detonation cell size is the evidence of interaction between shock waves in the front as shown in Figure 1.5. It is most widely used metric describing the dynamics of the detonation. The width of the cell size, which is usually used as a scale, is marked by λ . Many other parameters, such as critical tube diameter and critical initiation energy are given as a multiple of λ . Mixtures which are more prone to develop detonation have smaller cells than those resistive ones, thereby the cell width of a detonation in atmospheric stoichiometric hydrogen-air mixture is 8 mm [52–54], methane: 350 mm [55], ethyne (acetylene): 9.2 mm [56], ethene: 25.7 mm [57], ethane: 54 mm [56], propane: 46 mm [56, 58]. As one could expect the size of the cell is dependent on mixture composition (fuel, oxydizer, inert gas, equivalence ratio - Figure 1.6, inert gas fraction) and initial conditions (pressure, temperature), so at least 7 parameters control the detonation cell size and hence the detonation dynamics.

Figure 1.5. Cartoons and photographs of a detonation propagating from left to right. **Top:** Cartoons by Oppenheim [44] presenting interaction of 3 shock waves in the triple point and a soot foil. **Middle & Bottom:** Schlieren photograph and a soot foil of a detonation in $2\text{H}_2\text{-O}_2\text{-17Ar}$ (middle) and $\text{H}_2\text{-N}_2\text{O-1.33N}_2$ (bottom), with initial pressure 20 kPa taken by Austin and Shepherd in 2003 [45, 46] (the field of view is about 146 mm).

Figure 1.6. Detonation cell width of different fuel-air mixtures at atmospheric pressure. The solid lines represent the linear relationship $\lambda = A \cdot l$ (l is the induction zone width and is computed from detailed chemical kinetics). Taken from [59]

Naturally, researchers and engineers have been working on the development of phenomenological correlations of cell size using values which can be computed from the ZND model and the CJ theory, as they cannot calculate it directly from the theories. In 1965, Schelkin and Troshin [60] suggested that there exists a simple empirical proportionality factor (A) between the detonation cell width (λ) and the induction zone width (l). However, quantitative agreement of calculated and experimental λ is poor, but still within one order of magnitude [59], as shown in Figure 1.6.

In 2000, Gavrikov et al. [61] performed a comprehensive study of the cell sizes of different single-fuel mixtures (H_2 , CH_4 , C_2H_4 , C_2H_6) in air, humid air, O_2 -Ar and O_2 - N_2 . They developed a well-known, now semi-empirical, correlation taking as inputs

two stability parameters (nondimensional activation energy and a ratio of von Neumann temperature to initial temperature) and a characteristic reaction zone width, δ , calculated from detailed chemical kinetics mechanisms (Shepherd mechanism [62]) and the ZND model. The surface representing the formula is presented in Figure 1.7. Later, in 2017, Yu et al. [63] noticed that the formula is incapable of predicting λ for equivalence ratios larger than 2. They utilized the Gavrikov’s idea and created a model using the Support Vector Regression (SVR, a Machine Learning algorithm) with one additional parameter, the ratio of the postshock pressure to the initial pressure P_{PS}/P_0 , to improve regression in this study. However, one needs to notice that these correlations do not give information on the detonation structure regularity and, following on from that, no cell size distribution. Actually, this is due to how experimental cells are measured. Often the measurement is arguable, such as in highly irregular patterns where the selection of the model cell is difficult and its interpretation may vary between experimentalists. A good demonstration of this hurdle is shown in Figure 1.5 *bottom*, where a soot-foil of a detonation of $\text{H}_2\text{-N}_2\text{O-1.33N}_2$ with very irregular structure including substructures is shown and it may be arguable which cell is representative of the mixture and condition. One can deduce that due to different levels of *regularity* in detonation cell structure, mixtures with the *same* cell size may behave differently and, in fact, mixtures with irregular structure may be found to be more sensitive.

As summarized by Lee [59] in 1984 and what is still true after more than 30 years, the use of three-dimensional CFD (computational fluid dynamics) simulations to obtain cellular structure and cell size is not practical due to computational time and storage capacity, and the most convenient way of determining the cell width upto date is direct experimental measurement and use of the soot-foil technique. However, due to the above mentioned subjective nature concerning measurements of λ and limitations of test facilities in space and conditions, not all mixtures can be comprehensively examined experimentally and in these places correlations like Gavrikov’s and Yu’s are of great help.

Detonation cell structure irregularity

The behavior of detonation is controlled not only by the cell size but also by the level of cell regularity [64, 51, 65–67]. Kuznetsov et al. [68] experimentally showed that mixtures with highly irregular detonation cellular structures are much more prone to undergo

Figure 1.7. Ratio of λ/δ as a function of stability parameters: nondimensional activation energy E_a/RT_{PS} and a parameter describing the relation between chemical energy and the initial thermal energy of the mixture T_{vN}/T_0 . The surface shows the function developed by Gavrikov et al. (Black point bars - points above the surface, white point bars - points below the surface.) [61]

deflagration to detonation transition (DDT) compared to mixtures with regular structure with the same values of detonation cell sizes.

Radulescu et al. [69] proposed a stability parameter χ accounting for mixture detonability resulting from regularity of the detonation structure. According to the authors the parameter can be used to categorize the propensity of a detonable mixture to undergo the deflagration to detonation transition, the propensity for engine knock and the propensity for shocks to amplify in a reactive medium. The χ parameter is a multiplication of well-known stability parameters: non-dimensional activation energy, non-dimensional heat release and the ratio of ignition delay time to reaction time:

$$\chi = \frac{E_a}{RT} \frac{Q}{RT} \frac{\tau}{\tau_r} \quad (1.9)$$

Ng et al. [70] and Leung et al. [71] numerically investigated the role of χ in detonation stability. They showed that χ equal to 50–100 indicates the onset of instability. Jach and Teodorczyk [72] showed that calculations of λ and χ may be a good approach when

analyzing more complex mixtures difficult to measure experimentally. They investigated the exhaust gas influence on detonability of fresh gas (Figure 1.8). They concluded that a small amount of exhaust gases may significantly advance the detonability of a mixture.

Figure 1.8. Influence of combustion products molar fraction X_{CP} in the investigated syngas-air mixture on detonability parameters. The minimum of the detonation cell width is for $X_{CP} = 2\%$ and equals 4.8 mm, when for the mixture without combustion products it is 7.2 mm. The minimum of τ is for $X_{CP} = 6\%$ and it is equal to 0.376 μs , when for $X_{CP} = 0\%$ it is 0.598 μs .

1.2 Deflagration to Detonation Transition, DDT

As noted by Urtiew and Oppenheim [73] in 1966, the process of deflagration to detonation transition had been a subject of interest for many researchers since the discovery of the detonation wave in 1880's. The significant advancements in the theory of DDT were brought by the development of visualization and photographic techniques. The first true milestone in exploring the process was the invention and development of the high-speed mirror camera and the wave-speed camera (Figure 1.9) in 1920's and 1930's mainly by Payman, Woodhead and Titman [74, 75] and Fraser [76], which allowed direct observations of wave interactions associated with the initiation and development of the process. Different mechanisms of detonation initiation were proposed back then. In 1935, Bone, Fraser and Wheeler [76] postulated that the detonation is initiated and maintained as the result of self-ignition of the shock-compressed medium by the "*intensively radiating flame-front*".

Figure 1.9. **Top:** Schlieren system of the wave-speed camera built by Payman and Woodhead in 1931 [74]. The method applied in the camera consists of photographing on a vertically moving film, the horizontal movement of an atmospheric disturbance and continuous source of illumination. The photographic film, 7 cm wide, was stretched on a duraluminum drum, 1 m in circumference. The average rate of drum rotation was nearly 70 revolutions per second. **Bottom:** Fraser high-speed mirror camera [76]. In this camera the film is held stationary and the image of the flame is rotated in a plane perpendicular to the axis of the explosion tube by means of a mirror.

Further advancements in photographic technique enabled the work of Greifer et al. [77], who undertook a detailed streak Schlieren photographic investigation using a rotating mirror camera and precision optics. They observed that compression waves generated during the early stages of flame propagation strengthen into shock waves traveling ahead of the flame front (called *non-steady detonation* by the authors). In the next stage, this combination of decoupled flame front and shock waves narrowed generating new combustion centers ahead of the flame front. Finally, when stable detonation was initiated, the flame front overtook the shock wave and supplied it directly with energy from chemical reactions. They found that the structure of non-steady detonation is different from steady detonation in terms of the distance between the leading shock wave and the zone of chemical reactions. For a non-steady detonation, it was several centimeters, where for the steady state detonation, the distance could not be resolved by the optical system (indicating distances less than 1 mm).

As the length required for the flame to accelerate to the detonation depends on a mixture, Bollinger et al. [78] performed experimental measurement of induction distances in 15 mm and 50 mm diameter tubes (3 m long) for mixtures containing hydrogen, acetylene, methane or carbon monoxide diluted in nitrogen, argon, helium or carbon dioxide with oxygen. They carried out a brief discussion of the role of heat of combustion, flame temperature, burning velocity, sonic velocity and turbulence in the induction distance and as a result they came up with an empirical relationship as a function of the combustion temperature, burning velocity, sonic velocity in the unburned gas and Reynolds number:

$$K = Re_0 \frac{S_0 T_1}{a_0 T_0} \quad (1.10)$$

However they noted that the correlation is not reliable for mixtures containing hydrocarbons, pointing out limited experimental results concerning the effect of tube diameter in their study.

Then, in 1960's two experimental techniques became available. The first, mentioned before, proposed by Denisov and Troshin, utilizes the fact that the detonation front can write on the wall, leaving a cellular pattern behind. The second technique allowed very short light pulses (less than 10^{-8} s) with an ultrahigh repetition rate (up to 10^6 per second) to be used as the light source for Schlieren photography, thus giving a stroboscopic effect [73]. Oppenheim and Urtiew [73] performed ingenious experiments of deflagration to detonation transition in stoichiometric hydrogen-oxygen mixture taking stroboscopic photographs with use of laser light source. It was clear for them, that the initiation of detonation was caused by the *explosion in the explosion* which then spread as a spherical detonation in postshock gas. A detonation's reflection from the walls generated the backward propagating detonation wave, as well as the transverse waves bouncing between the side walls. Subsequently, the spherical detonation soon became a planar detonation wave, with its characteristic multi-wave structure. Although a given elucidation of DDT was solid and gave a general understanding of the process, it did not indicate its exact origin.

At the end of 1980's, Lee et al. [79–81] refined the idea of *the explosion in the explosion* as the *self-initiation* mechanism of detonation and proposed the now well-known

term SWACER, which stands for Shock Wave Amplification by Coherent Energy Release. Actually, they experimentally observed this phenomenon, which was 10 years earlier theoretically suggested by Zel'dovich et al. [82–84]. The idea of the SWACER is that the compression wave (or shock wave) is synchronized with the chemical energy release, so that the energy is fed in exact time to the generated shock wave [81]. These generated shock waves coalesce forming stronger shocks, which soon are able to ignite a mixture ahead of them.

The DDT process presented in Figure 1.10 can be divided into 4 phases after Shepherd and Lee [85].

Mild ignition and laminar flame. The initial flame is developed by a relatively small energy source, e.g. spark. The flame is a subsonic combustion wave, in which pressure and density decrease across the front. The flame propagates by means of molecular transport of energy and free radicals from the reaction zone to the unburned mixture ahead of it. Flame speed depends on the initial composition of the mixture and the thermodynamic conditions.

Turbulent flame and acceleration. When the flame front expands and its surface becomes bigger, a higher amount of energy is fed to the front, thereby increasing its velocity. The flame firstly becomes wrinkled and then turbulent due to its interactions with obstacles and walls. The accelerating combustion front generates acoustic waves, which coalesce into pressure waves and then shock waves. Natural instability mechanisms, such as Rayleigh-Taylor, Richtmyer-Meshkov, and Kelvin-Helmholtz, become responsible for the the continuous increase of the flame surface area, the energy release rate, flame speed, and thereby the strength of leading shock wave. In this stage, the flame front is extensively distorted, forming a *flame brush*. The flame is in the *distributed reaction zone* regime. This feedback mechanism accelerates the flame up to 1000 m/s

Formation of explosion centers. The flame brush starts to be composed of volumetrically-exploding pockets. These exploding pockets generate pressure waves, which coalesce into weak shock waves ahead of the flame, though these shock waves are still too weak to trigger self-ignition of a fresh mixture and to trigger detonation directly. The ignition delay times behind the leading shock wave are too long, hence the acoustic and the reaction fronts

are uncoupled. Nevertheless, the temperature behind the leading shock wave is able to initiate a slow reaction process. This partially-reacted medium becomes progressively more reactive and unstable, when the pressure-wave effects accumulate.

Formation of a detonation wave. The detonation wave is formed when the reaction wave and the leading shock wave couple, and by the same token the ignition delay time behind the shock wave is short enough. The explosion of the reactants happens closely enough to the leading shock wave that the explosion drives the shock wave and the system becomes self-sustaining. The conditions when DDT takes place are still not well understood, hence the prediction of quantities such as the exact location of the transition are unreliable in many applications.

Figure 1.10. Computed flame evolution by Kessler, Gamezo and Oran [86, 87]. Flame propagates in an obstructed channel filled with a stoichiometric methane-air mixture. The channel height is 52 cm. Computational domain is 102 cm by 26 cm, hence the half of the channel height is used as computational domain.

Critical conditions for DDT in obstructed channels were extensively studied by many researchers due to their fundamental and practical importance. Teodorczyk et al. [88, 89] performed experimental studies in a narrow channel to minimize three-dimensional effects and simplify complex shock wave interactions. They noticed that obstacles play a dual role. They attenuate the detonation by diffraction and by the generated expansion waves they decouple the reaction zone from the shock wave, causing the detonation to fail. On the other hand, they help to reinitiate the detonation by providing additional surface for shock reflection. In this sense a *quasi-detonation* takes place. In general, obstacles were found to play a negative role in the average propagation velocity of the detonation. They showed that the main mechanism of transition to detonation is due to shock reflections.

Dorofeev, Kuznetsov and co-workers [90, 68, 91, 92] performed extensive experimental studies on effect of scale and regularity of cellular structure of detonation on the onset of detonations. They followed a trend of comparing characteristic geometrical sizes with the chemical length scales of the mixture, represented by detonation cell width (λ). A criterion for the onset of detonations called 7λ was formulated meaning that the characteristic size of a room filled with a flammable mixture has to be larger than 7λ . Experiments performed at McGill University by Peraldi et al. [93] revealed that the minimum transverse dimension in the tube has to be of the order of, or larger than, λ . Hence, the larger the confinement the wider the composition range of mixtures which can undergo DDT.

1.3 Reaction Kinetics Basics

The overall chemical process can be described by a single stoichiometric equation [94]. The stoichiometric equation defines the molar ratio of the reacting species and the reaction products. Real chemical systems corresponding to such a single chemical reaction are very rare in reality. In most cases, the reaction of the reactants into the final products are formed at the end of many coupled reaction steps. Each of the individual steps is called an elementary reaction. Within elementary reactions, there is no macroscopically observable intermediate between the reactants and the products.

Taking hydrogen oxidation as an example its overall reaction can be written as:

If A_j is the formula of the j th species in the overall reaction equation and ν_j is the stoichiometric coefficient of the j th species, then the general stoichiometric equation is:

$$0 = \sum_{j=1}^{N_s} \nu_j A_j, \quad (1.11)$$

Then if Y_j is the molar concentration of the j th species the rate of a chemical reaction can be formulated as:

$$r = \frac{1}{\nu_j} \frac{dY_j}{dt}, \quad (1.12)$$

Reaction rate r is independent of index j . This means that the same reaction rate is obtained when the production rate of any of the species is measured. However, the reaction rate depends on a given form of the stoichiometric equation. The reaction rate r can always be approximated by:

$$r = k \prod_{j=1}^{N_s} Y_j^{\alpha_j} \quad (1.13)$$

where k is called the rate coefficient, α_j is called the reaction order with respect to species A_j and N_s is the number of species. The rate coefficient k is independent of the concentrations but may depend on temperature, pressure and the quality and quantity of the nonreactive species present (e.g. an inert dilution gas).

In order to define the time-dependent dynamics of a system accurately, a reaction model should include steps where intermediate species are formed from reactants and then go on to form products. For example, detailed reaction mechanisms for the oxidation of hydrogen contain not only the reactants and products but also several intermediates (H, O, OH, HO₂, H₂O₂), which are present in the 30-40 reaction steps considered. The number of elementary reaction steps within a kinetic reaction mechanism can typically vary from ten to tens of thousands, depending on the chemical process, the reaction conditions and the required detail and accuracy of the chemical kinetic model. The size of detailed reaction mechanisms and its dependence on targeted species is visualized in Figure 1.11 (diagram

Figure 1.11. Mechanism size. Correlation between number of reactions and number of species for various published kinetic models [95, 1, 96]. Taken from [95].

was initially created by T.F. Lu and C.K. Law [96], researchers tend to update it [95, 1]).

Each elementary reaction step i can be characterized by the following stoichiometric equation:

$$\sum_j \nu_{ij}^L A_j = \sum_j \nu_{ij}^R A_j \quad (1.14)$$

where the stoichiometric coefficients on the left-hand side (ν_{ij}^L) and the right-hand side (ν_{ij}^R) of an elementary reaction step should be distinguished. The stoichiometric coefficient belonging to species i in a reaction step can be obtained from the equation $\nu_{ij} = \nu_{ij}^R - \nu_{ij}^L$. The stoichiometric coefficients can be obtained by the *lumping* of several elementary reactions.

A detailed kinetic reaction mechanism contains the stoichiometric equations of type (1.14) and the corresponding rate coefficient for each reaction step. Instead of the equality sign, arrows are used for one-way or irreversible chemical reactions (like $A \rightarrow B$). Reversible reactions are denoted by double arrows (like $A \rightleftharpoons B$). These rate coefficients can be physical constants that are valid for the conditions of the reactions (e.g. temperature, pressure) or functions that can be used to calculate the value of the rate coefficient applicable at the

actual temperature, pressure, gas composition, etc. Hence, each mechanism usually has its own validity ranges.

1.3.1 Experimental Determination of Reaction Rate

For the determination of rate coefficient at constant volume the concentration of a chosen reactant or product is determined at various time intervals. The change in concentration ΔY_j for a given time interval Δt is obtained. An average rate of reaction is then obtained by calculating $\Delta Y_j/\Delta t$. The smaller the value of Δt , the closer the value of the rate will be to the real rate at time $(t_1 + t_2)/2$ because

$$\lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta Y_j}{\Delta t} \rightarrow \frac{dY_j}{dt} \quad (1.15)$$

The rate coefficient can also be obtained by plotting concentration of reactant or product against time and measuring the slope of the curve dY_j/dt at required time. The rate of reaction obtained from such method is known as instantaneous rate. The concentration of the reactant or product varies exponentially or linearly with time [97].

1.3.2 The Law of Mass Action

The law of mass action was first proposed by Guldberg and Waage in 1864 in Oslo, Norway. In spite of the importance of the law in chemistry and contributions to the knowledge of both equilibrium and rate coefficients, the first presentation of Guldberg's and Waage's work was either unnoticed or criticized [98]. The law is the mathematical basis for the quantitative description of the reaction, and is the fundamental postulate of the chemical kinetics. In kinetic formulation this law expresses the proportionality between the rate and the concentrations of the reagents:

$$r_i = k_i \prod_j^{N_s} Y_j^{\nu_{ij}^L}, \quad (1.16)$$

where r_i and k_i are the rate and the rate coefficient, respectively, of the i th reaction step. Equation 1.16 is similar to 1.13, but here the exponent is not an empirical value (the reaction order), but the corresponding stoichiometric coefficient. If the law of mass action is valid, the overall order of reaction step i is equal to $\sum_j \nu_{ij}^L$. In many cases, the law of

mass action is assumed to be also applicable for non-elementary reaction steps, but it is not always the case that a lumped reaction follows the law of mass action [94]. The kinetic system of ordinary differential equations (ODEs) defines the relationship between the production rates of the species and rates of the reaction step r_i :

$$\frac{dY_j}{dt} = \sum_i^{N_s} \nu_{ij} r_i = f_i \quad (1.17)$$

This means that number of equations in the kinetic systems of ODEs is equal to the number of species in the reaction mechanism. These equations are coupled and therefore can only be solved simultaneously. The goal of chemical mechanism reduction is to limit the number of required intermediates within the mechanism in order to reduce the number of ODEs required to accurately represent the time-dependent behaviour of key species.

In adiabatic systems or in systems with a known heat loss rate, usually temperature is added as the $(N_s + 1)$ th variable of the kinetic system of ODEs. The differential equation for the rate of change of temperature in a closed homogeneous reaction vessel is given as

$$C_p \frac{dT}{dt} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_R} \Delta_r H_i^\Phi r_i - \frac{\zeta S}{V} (T - T_0) \quad (1.18)$$

where T is the actual temperature of the system, T_0 is the ambient temperature (e.g. the temperature of the lab), C_p is the constant pressure heat capacity of the mixture, $\Delta_r H_i^\Phi$ is the standard molar reaction enthalpy of reaction step i , S and V are the surface and the volume of the system, respectively, and ζ is the heat transfer coefficient between the system and its surroundings. The change in temperature can be calculated together with the change in concentrations as part of the coupled ODE system. The kinetic system of ODEs is first-order and usually nonlinear, since it contains first-order derivatives with respect to time and the time derivative is usually a nonlinear function of concentrations. Each species participates in several reactions; therefore, the production rates of the species are coupled. The rates of the reaction steps can be very different and may span many (even 10-25) orders of magnitude. Such differential equations are called stiff ODEs. This set of ODEs represents an autonomous system, as the time in the kinetic system is a relative time from the beginning of the experiment.

In order to describe an influence of chemical reactions on the system the Jacobian matrix is solved:

$$\mathbf{J} = \left\{ \frac{\partial f_i}{\partial Y_j} \right\} \quad (1.19)$$

where f_i is the chemical source term from Eq. 1.17. The Jacobian is of great use in the mechanism reduction process, being the basis of local sensitivity analysis of each species in the mechanism. If the reaction mechanism consists of zeroth-order and first-order reaction steps only, then the elements of the Jacobian are constant real numbers. In all other cases, the elements of the Jacobian depend on the concentration of species Y .

The Order of Reactions

The kinetic investigation of a reaction is carried out to establish the rate law and to measure the rate coefficients. The first step is to identify or examine the role of each component, e.g. to determine the order of reaction with respect to each reactant or product. There are various methods, which can be used to determine the order of reaction with respect to a reactant, however, every method requires essentially the measurement of concentration of the reactant or product at various time intervals [97]. One of the methods used to assess the order of the reaction is the differential method, called Van't Hoff's differential method.

The rate of chemical reaction for i.e. a zeroth-order, first-order and second-order chemical reaction with a single reactant is given by

$$-\frac{dY_j}{dt} = kY_j^a \quad (1.20)$$

where a is equal to 0, 1 or 2, respectively.

Zeroth order with respect to a particular reactant means that the chemical reaction does not depend on the concentration of that reactant. This can occur when the reactant is not involved in the slowest step of the reaction, or when the reaction rate depends on the adsorption of a particular reactant by a fully covered catalyst surface. Since the surface is saturated, the reaction rate does not depend on the concentration of the adsorbed reactant [99].

1.3.3 Reaction Kinetics of Detonation

High temperature chemistry ($T > 1200$ K) controls the propagation of gaseous detonations. According to Westbrook [100] and Shepherd [45], thermodynamic conditions appearing behind the detonation wave most closely are reproduced in shock tube experiments. Westbrook describes the ignition in shock tubes as a two-phase process: first there is an initial period of generation of radicals (O and OH), followed by a period of very rapid, exponential production of radicals. The dominant high temperature chain-branching reaction controlling this process is when one H atom is consumed and two radicals are produced, namely O and OH [100]:

Many reactions in the combustion are chain reactions. In a chain reaction, a radical produced in one step generates a radical in a subsequent step, then that radical generates another radical, and so on. The radicals are species with unpaired electrons.

Hydrogen explosion

Early works of Semenov [101] and Hinshelwood [102], which brought the Nobel Prize for Chemistry in 1956 to both "for their research into the mechanisms of chemical reactions, notably the mechanisms of chain and branched-chain chemical reactions", established the chain character of reaction of the $\text{H}_2\text{-O}_2$ system. Thermal explosion is a very rapid reaction arising from a rapid increase of reaction rate with increasing temperature. The temperature of the systems rises if the energy released by an exothermic reaction cannot escape, and the reaction goes faster. The acceleration of the rate results in an even faster rise of temperature, so the reaction becomes catastrophically fast. A chain-branching explosion occurs when the number of chain centers grows exponentially [103].

Some steps from hydrogen oxidation are as follows:

A branching step is an elementary reaction that produces more than one chain carrier. The occurrence of an explosion depends on the temperature and pressure of the system, and the explosion regions for the reaction. Radicals combine and end the chain in the termination step [103].

Chain reactions in the hydrocarbon combustion

As explained by Westbrook [100] the chain character of the reaction of $\text{H}_2\text{-O}_2$ applies to hydrocarbon oxidation. Initiation reactions generate radicals from stable species, e.g. the decomposition of propane:

Then, chain propagation reactions maintain the number of radicals, e.g. here, when OH is consumed and an ethyl radical is produced:

Chain termination reduces the number of radicals, as in recombination producing stable butane:

The key to understanding ignition kinetics is to identify the chain branching steps under the conditions being studied. In chain branching reactions, the number of radicals increases, e.g. consuming one O atom and producing two radicals, O and OH in the R3 reaction of hydrogen explosion.

Frequently chain properties are attributed to a sequence of reactions. As shown below, the sequence of two reactions produces three radicals - propane and hydroperoxy radicals are consumed and a propyl radical and two hydroxyl radicals are produced:

There are much longer sequences of reactions for which their chain properties become evident later.

The most important high temperature chain branching reaction consumes one H atom and produces two radicals (R3 reaction of hydrogen explosion). H atoms are produced by thermal decomposition of radicals, e.g. ethyl radical. Activation energies of these reaction is high, so they need high temperatures to proceed (for R3 16.8 kcal/mol).

Not all radical species have the same influence on the overall reaction rate, due to subsequent reactions with different branching characteristics. For example, in this region production of ethyl radicals accelerates the overall rate of ignition because C_2H_5 produces H atoms:

while production of methyl radicals decreases the overall rate of ignition at high temperatures because methyl radicals recombine:

resulting in chain termination. The specific reaction sequences are dependent on the temperature, pressure and reactant composition change leading to the chain branching change. At temperatures above 850 K but below 1200 K, the R3 reaction of hydrogen explosion is too slow to provide sufficient branching rates for ignition, and a different reaction path dominates. Key reactions include the R6 reaction of hydrogen explosion and:

where RH is an alkane, and R is an alkyl radical. This set of reactions conditions knocking combustion in spark ignition engines, ignition in liquid-fueled diesel engines and operation of engines in HCCI mode (homogeneous charge, compression ignition).

1.4 Ignition delay time measurement in Shock Tube

The first shock tube was constructed by Vieille in 1899 in France during his study of combustion and detonation [23, 104]. Soon it became the most important measuring and testing device in high-temperature gas dynamics research. One of the first applications of shock tubes was the simulation of blast waves from nuclear explosions and the study of

interactions of shock waves with scaled architectural structures (models of houses, planes, cars) during Cold War. The main driver was the constant threat of the use of nuclear blasts against civil and military installations. Nevertheless, the shock tube has proven to be most useful in chemical kinetics and detonation studies.

1.4.1 Shock Tube theory

A shock tube is an experimental apparatus where high pressure and high temperature of a test gas are obtained as a result of passage of a shock wave. Figure 1.12 shows the $x - t$ diagram with trajectories of the waves, as well as pressure and temperature profiles in time t' (before the incident wave reflects from the end wall). The shock wave is generated when a diaphragm isolating a low-pressure test section from a high-pressure driver section is removed. The incident shock wave travels towards the end wall in the test gas in its initial state, producing post-shock conditions. Then, after hitting the wall the reflected shock wave propagates in the shocked gas generating the reflected shock condition in the test gas. This is the onset of the period when self-ignition of the test gas is aimed to take place. Soon the reflected wave meets with the contact surface which it reflects off of and comes back to the end wall, thereby ending the observation time. Ignition delay time may be defined as the time interval between the pressure rise caused by the reflected shock and the onset of ignition. Different definitions of the delay time are used in literature.

It is assumed that the gas behind the reflected shock wave (5) is stationary and characterized by well-defined conditions. The conditions are suitable for accurate chemical kinetic studies [105]. Its temperature T_5 and pressure P_5 can be calculated using theoretical relationships knowing the Mach of incident shock wave, the initial conditions in the test section (1) and the heat capacity ratio of the test gas γ :

$$\frac{P_5}{P_1} = \left(\frac{2\gamma M_1^2 - (\gamma - 1)}{\gamma + 1} \right) \left(\frac{(3\gamma - 1)M_1^2 - 2(\gamma - 1)}{(\gamma - 1)M_1^2 + 2} \right) \quad (1.21)$$

$$\frac{T_5}{T_1} = \frac{(2(\gamma - 1)M_1^2 + (3 - \gamma))((3\gamma - 1)M_1^2 - 2(\gamma - 1))}{(\gamma + 1)^2 M_1^2} \quad (1.22)$$

Figure 1.12. **Top:** $x-t$ diagram. **Middle:** Pressure profile. **Bottom:** Temperature profile. (1) Initial state of test gas. (2) Shocked gas. (3) Driver gas behind the contact surface. (4) Initial state of driver gas. (5) Test gas in reflected shock condition. Taken from [106].

1.4.2 Non-ideal effects in Shock Tube

The non-idealities in shock tubes are caused by technical difficulties (e.g., imperfect diaphragm burst) and fluid dynamics non-idealities (e.g., boundary layer build up and reflected shock bifurcation, the reflected shock wave interaction with the contact surface). Traditionally these non-idealities are mitigated by use of monoatomic driver gases and testing highly diluted mixtures.

Interaction of reflected shock wave with contact surface

The observation time length in a typical shock tube is 1–3 ms and is limited by the arrival of the contact surface and the collision with the reflected shock wave. The result of collision is seen as a *bump* in the pressure profile. This effect can be eliminated by contact surface tailoring, that is by equilibrating the acoustic impedances of the gases in states (2) and (3): $\rho_2 a_2 = \rho_3 a_3$. Thereby the reflected shock wave propagates through the contact surface without reflection and any disturbance. The tailoring of the contact surface is obtained by a proper selection of driver gas composition (a mixture of different fractions of argon, nitrogen and helium is used). Additionally, a portion of buffer gas (e.g., helium) between the diaphragm and the test mixture is utilized as well.

Boundary layer growth

The boundary layer builds up behind an incident shock wave as it propagates along the shock tube. The boundary layer behind the incident shock wave causes a slight increase of temperature and pressure in the core of test gas. The incident shock wave attenuates. Initially it has very little effect on shock tube conditions, however when the reflected shock wave propagates in the opposite direction, it interacts with the growing boundary layer causing a temperature and pressure increase. This increase happens to be linear with observation time. In the end, it results in a change of apparent activation energy of ignition delay times. The boundary layer effect is quantified by the relative change of pressure: $1/P_5 \cdot dP_5/dt$ [%/ms]. It can be minimized by utilizing shock tubes with large diameters and by a driver section insert.

Boundary layer growth is a source of one more non-ideality: the reflected shock wave bifurcation. The wave bifurcates in the boundary layer into two oblique shocks, forming a lambda shape. The bifurcation height is larger when the amount of di- and polyatomic molecules is high. This introduces uncertainty in the recording of the arrival time of the reflected shock wave by pressure transducers, usually located on the cylindrical wall of the shock tube [107]. Hence, measured ignition delay time by the side-wall sensor has to be corrected.

Figure 1.13. Influence of shock tailoring, insert and buffer gas on observation time (nonreactive pressure traces are shown - without ignition). Taken from [105].

Mitigating non-ideality effects in shock tubes results in longer observation time and lower measurement uncertainty. Figure 1.13 shows how applying contact surface tailoring, the application of an insert, and the use of buffer gas has extended observation time from 1 ms up to 2.5 ms in the shock tube at ICARE, CNRS (Orléans, France) [105].

1.4.3 Measurement technique

Two types of ignition indicators are utilized in the literature: pressure increase or radical chemiluminescence [108]. Pressure transducers are located on the end wall or the sidewall close to the end of the tube. Figure 1.14 shows pressure traces from both sensors. The sidewall sensor (black line) sees three pressure increases. The first one is caused by the incident shock wave passage, the second is the arrival of the reflected shock wave and the last one is self-ignition. The green line presents the recording of the end-wall sensors in

the same experiment. Two pressure increases are visible: the reflection of the wave and the ignition. However, in the case of mixtures with low fuel concentration pressure rise is low and often unclear, as noise generated by mechanical vibrations becomes significant. In this case, use of radical chemiluminescence is preferred technique.

Figure 1.14. End-wall (green line, CFT) and sidewall (black line, CS) pressure transducers readings. Pressure increase over observation time dP/dt is calculated for both sensors. Due to the incident shock wave attenuation along the tube, the shock velocity is extrapolated at the end wall. P_5 linear (grey horizontal line) and P_5 deg2 (red horizontal line) indicate reflected shock pressure calculated for a linear and a quadratic velocity extrapolation. Taken from unpublished Author's work.

Chemiluminescence is emission of the light by excited species as they relax to the ground state (e.g., $\text{OH}^* \rightarrow \text{OH} + h\nu$). It is widely used as a marker of heat release rate in flame. The most commonly used radicals are OH^* , CH^* and C_2^* , reaching maximum emissions around 306, 430 and 516 nm in wavelength space, respectively. Figure 1.15 presents OH^* trace (red line) and resulting ignition delay time.

Figure 1.15. **Top:** End-wall sensor pressure profile (black line) and OH* profile (red line). **Bottom:** Pressure profile recorded by the pressure transducer located opposite the quartz optical window and the photomultiplier. Two definitions of ignition delay time are presented: 50% of OH* maximum $t_{50\%OH}$ and pressure tangential method $t_{dp/dt}$. Taken from unpublished Author's work.

1.5 Assessment of detailed reaction mechanisms

One of the first studies on the accuracy of detailed reaction mechanisms for detonation simulation was performed by Schultz and Shepherd [109] at CALTECH and by Teodorczyk et al. [110] at WUT in 2000. The approach of both works was analogous. In total, their analyses concerned shock tube delay times of 8 types of fuel: H₂, CH₄-C₃H₈, C₂H₂, C₂H₄, C₆H₆ (benzene) and C₇H₈ (toluene). These IDTs were simulated by 21 detailed reaction mechanisms utilizing a constant-volume explosion model. For quantitative assessment of the mechanisms the average deviation was formulated as follows:

$$D = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \log \frac{IDT_{S,j}}{IDT_{E,j}} \quad (1.23)$$

They presented the average deviation calculated over temperature ranges of 100 K against temperature. An exemplary diagram summarizing the performance of the Konnov mechanism is shown in Figure 1.16.

Figure 1.16. Deviation of ignition delay time for the Konnov (1998) mechanism. Taken from [109]. Zero represents a perfect match to experiment.

Olm et al. [111–113] at ELTE adopted a more extended study for hydrogen and syngas combustion without targeting any special conditions. They analyzed the performance of mechanisms in reproducing of ignition delay time from both shock tubes and rapid compression machines (RCM), with laminar burning velocities and concentration profiles. Their approach was based on the Sum of Squared Errors and the objective function was defined as follows:

$$E_i = \frac{1}{N_i} \sum_{j=1}^{N_i} \left(\frac{Y_{ij}^{sim} - Y_{ij}^{exp}}{\sigma(Y_i^{exp,j})} \right)^2 \quad (1.24)$$

$$E = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N E_i \quad (1.25)$$

where N is the number of datasets and N_i is the number of points in the i th dataset. Values Y_{ij}^{exp} and $\sigma(Y_{ij}^{exp})$ are the j th data point and its standard deviation, respectively, in the i th dataset. Y_{ij}^{sim} denotes the corresponding modeled value using an appropriate mechanism and simulation method. In the case of ignition delay time Y was equal to natural logarithm of IDT, $Y_{ij} = \ln IDT$. In the majority of collected experimental data sets pressure-time histories were not present, therefore the authors assumed constant volume and adiabatic conditions. Hence, they were not able to take into account facility effects. Alternatively, they decided to exclude low temperature data ($T < 1000K$) from their analysis, hence

leaving in the analysis only IDTs shorter than 1–2 ms. Rapid compression machine IDTs were simulated using the volume-time histories recalculated from experimental pressure profiles published with the IDTs. Experiments lacking published heat loss data were excluded from their comparison. The authors presented error across either temperature, pressure, CO/H₂ ratio (in the case of syngas in [113]), equivalence ratio, diluent concentration, diluent type or experimental method. An exemplary diagram is shown in Figure 1.17 for the performance of the mechanisms for various ranges of temperature and pressure with respect to syngas ignition delay time.

Figure 1.17. Error of the reproduction of syngas ignition delay times according to temperature and pressure. Each plot shows the result for shock tubes (left part), shock tubes using volume-time history (middle part) and rapid compression machines (right part). Grey region was excluded from analysis. Taken from [112].

Similar analyses were carried out at WUT by Jach, Rudy, Cieslak, Pekalski and Teodorczyk in [114–117] for hydrogen and C1–C5 hydrocarbons, 12 species in total. They utilized the error function presented in Eq. 1.23. Their study was focused on detonation relevant conditions, therefore only ignition delay times from shock tube experiments were taken into account. Within each subset of temperature, pressure, equivalence ratio and

dilution fraction the average error was calculated and plotted against these parameters. Additionally, they performed an analogous study for piston engine relevant conditions with respect to ignition delay times and laminar burning velocities. In [118] they investigated the influence of glycerol doping on gasoline and diesel fuel. Together with Pyszczek and Mazuro in [119], they numerically investigated low calorific syngas combustion in the opposed-piston engine.

Figure 1.18. Average error of reproduction of ethylene ignition delay time plotted against temperature and pressure. Right hand side plots show the number of experimental point in each subrange.

In 2016 at POLIMI, Bernardi et al. [120] proposed a Curve Matching method in order to compare the shapes of curves that are functional estimates of experimental and simulated values. Thereby, in the case of ignition delay times it became possible to analyze how well mechanisms reproduce the activation energy, and not only focusing on

absolute errors. They proposed different metrics measuring absolute deviation and shift along the x -axis of the original estimates and their first deviations. The method was used in [120] to assess mechanisms' performance for n-heptane. Jach et al. utilized the Curve Matching method for mechanisms' assessment for C1–C5 hydrocarbons, which was partially published in [121]. In Figure 1.19 exemplary estimates and alignment analysis for one set of methane IDTs are presented.

Figure 1.19. Experimental ignition delay times of $\text{CH}_4\text{-O}_2\text{-Ar}$ measured by Frank and Braun-Unkloff [122], their functional estimate and functional estimate of M2 (CaltechMech) and M11 (Polimi C1C3 LT HT 1412) mechanisms before and after x alignment. M11 is compared to M2, which performs best in this particular condition. Alignment of both mechanisms does not improve indices corresponding to the 1st derivative.

1.6 Objectives and Outline

The main motivation of this dissertation is to enable more reliable numerical investigations of deflagration to detonation transition. The first step, is to provide more insight into performance of detailed reaction mechanisms in reproducing ignition delay times of C1–C4 hydrocarbons and to propose a method of robust presentation of obtained results. The goal is to deliver comprehensive, multidimensional analysis of the problem and to undertake discussion on the statistical dispersion of results. In the second step, the goal is to develop an ignition delay time model based on an emerging technology, Deep Learning, and collected experimental IDTs. Ideally, calculations with the model should be faster

and as or more accurate than the best mechanism.

Ignition delay time is one of the main properties used for mechanism validation, together with laminar burning velocity and concentration measurements. The ignition delay times used in the assessment come from shock tube experiments and most of them lie within the range of high temperature chemistry. These experiments most closely represent the type of initial and thermodynamic conditions relevant to detonations [109].

Outline

Chapter 2 presents an assessment of detailed reaction mechanisms for the reproduction of ignition delay times. The presented analysis is the development of a paper already published by the Author [123] devoted to C2–C6 alkenes and acetylene. At the beginning of the Chapter, the Author briefly characterizes 15 DRMs which are the subject of the assessment. As some research groups provided DRMs that were designed in a hierarchical way, the Pearson linear correlation coefficient is calculated to assess to what extent results are similar within the group. Then, the analysis of experimental data collected as a result of an extensive literature review is carried out. The range and distribution of experimental conditions are discussed to better visualize the first and the most important parameter influencing mechanisms' validation. Some datasets are excluded from the analysis due to poor quality, as indicated by a proposed approach. Secondly, the ignition delay time calculation technique and the newly developed assessment method are introduced and its components described. Finally, in each subsection one hydrocarbon is elaborated on in an analogous manner, starting from the highest level of generality (the quantitative error parameters) then delving into the details (the box plots and the heat maps). A consolidated table with a summary of all DRMs and species is presented in the concluding section of the Chapter.

Chapter 3 presents the development process of the IDT model based on a Deep Neural Network. The reader is briefly introduced to Artificial Intelligence history and the Deep Learning concept. Two models are developed: one for argon diluted mixtures and a second for nitrogen. The models' output is natural logarithm of IDT, as a histogram of this parameters is less skewed than one of IDT. The experimental IDTs collected for the purpose of Chapter 2 are utilized for the models' training. Performance of the models

calculated for a randomly chosen test set (20% of the whole set) is better than NUIG n-Heptane and Polimi PRF PAH LT, in terms of the Pearson correlation coefficient, Mean Absolute Error and Mean Absolute Percentage Error. The computational time is much shorter as well, making the DNN models a reasonable choice for CFD calculations.

Chapter 2

Assessment of detailed reaction mechanisms for reproduction of ignition delay times

2.1 Detailed chemical kinetics mechanisms

The analysis includes 15 detailed chemical kinetics mechanisms: 5 mechanisms from NUI Galway, Combustion Chemistry Centre [124], 3 mechanisms from The CRECK Modeling Group, Politecnico di Milano [125], a mechanism from the FORCE group (CaltechMech) [126], the USC Combustion Kinetics Laboratory (USC Mech II and USC Mech C1-C3) [127], the UC San Diego [128], the JetSurF 2.0 and 2 older mechanisms - GRI-mech 3.0 and Konnov 0.5. The mechanisms are summarized in Table 2.1. Mechanism IDs are consistently used throughout the present Chapter.

It should be noted that many of these mechanisms have not been particularly developed for species addressed in the present Chapter. Some of the species are included in the mechanisms simply because they are intermediate species and it appears that no study has been specifically developed to study their ignition. In spite of this fact, the above-mentioned mechanisms are tested against the reproduction of ignition delay times of interest.

Table 2.1. Summary of mechanisms used. Mechanism IDs are consistently used throughout the present Chapter.

ID	Mechanism	Reference	Year of release	No of species
M1	AramcoMech2.0	[6, 13–18]	2013	493
M2	CaltechMech	[35–38]	2007	174
M3	USC Mech C1-C3	[129–132]	1999	71
M4	GRI-mech 3.0	[11]	1999	53
M5	Konnov 0.5	[12]	2000	127
M6	JetSurF 2.0	[133]	2010	348
M7	NUIG Butane	[134–138]	2010	230
M8	NUIG Pentane Isomers	[139–141]	2015	293
M9	NUIG n-Hexane	[142]	2015	1120
M10	NUIG n-Heptane	[143]	2016	1268
M11	Polimi C1C3 LT HT 1412	[39]	2014	107
M12	Polimi C1C3 HT NOx 1412	[39, 144–146]	2014	115
M13	Polimi PRF PAH LT	[147–150]	2009	176
M14	UC San Diego	[128]	2014	50
M15	USC Mech II	[40]	2007	111

Some of these mechanisms have been developed in a hierarchical manner [1], hence they are designed to give very similar results within the same group. This feature is tested by calculating the Pearson coefficient, which measures linear correlation between two sets of values. It is defined as follows:

$$\rho(x, y) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (2.1)$$

where x and y are vectors of ignition delay times obtained with tested mechanisms, n is the sample size (size of both samples is equal) and \bar{x} and \bar{y} are medians of x and y , respectively. Two types of Pearson coefficients are calculated. The first one ρ_{HC} is calculated for individual hydrocarbons (e.g., $\rho(M12, M13)_{C_3H_6} = 89.5\%$), while the second one ρ_{all} is obtained without distinction between hydrocarbons (e.g., $\rho(M3, M15)_{all} = 93.5\%$). In Table 2.2 both coefficients are summarized – in the top part ρ_{all} is shown, in the bottom part the minimum ρ_{HC} across addressed species. It is arbitrarily assumed that ρ higher than 95% indicates high correlation between mechanisms. High correlation between mechanisms from the CRECK Modeling Group is apparent (M11, M12, M13). The Pearson coefficients $\rho(M11, M12)_{all}$ and $\rho(M12, M13)_{all}$ reach values higher than the threshold. However, in the case of propene, M13 is less correlated with M11 and M12 – $\rho(M12, M13)_{C_3H_6} = 89.5\%$. Hence, M12 and M13 will remain in the analysis and M11 is

excluded. Within the NUI Galway group M1 and M10 give practically the same results ($\rho_{all} > 99\%$). This similarity is natural, as M10’s submechanism for C0–C4 fuels is taken from M1 [143]. Hence, M1 is excluded from the analysis, since M10 has a broader range of species included (up to C7 fuel, whereas M1 is up to C4 fuels).

Table 2.2. **Top triangle:** Pearson correlation coefficient ρ_{all} calculated without distinction between hydrocarbons. **Bottom triangle:** Minimum Pearson coefficient $\min_{HC}(\rho_{HC})$ across all analyzed hydrocarbons (green: $\rho = 1$, white: $\rho < 0.9$).

ρ	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15
M1	1.000	0.951	0.847	0.831	0.680	0.903	0.918	0.975	0.660	0.999	0.926	0.929	0.887	0.957	0.855
M2	0.798	1.000	0.886	0.852	0.845	0.894	0.929	0.919	0.515	0.896	0.889	0.890	0.875	0.957	0.925
M3	0.729	0.769	1.000	0.888	0.875	0.906	0.840	0.825	0.141	0.752	0.827	0.822	0.839	0.898	0.935
M4	0.648	0.662	0.729	1.000	0.769	0.803	0.819	0.821	0.673	0.767	0.813	0.820	0.812	0.878	0.798
M5	0.519	0.783	0.726	0.586	1.000	0.693	0.787	0.666	0.314	0.618	0.832	0.829	0.629	0.870	0.701
M6	0.795	0.733	0.800	0.618	0.678	1.000	0.844	0.784	0.396	0.742	0.878	0.876	0.748	0.951	0.945
M7	0.745	0.854	0.753	0.643	0.694	0.699	1.000	0.927	0.607	0.876	0.914	0.916	0.817	0.916	0.867
M8	0.841	0.854	0.729	0.646	0.533	0.693	0.851	1.000	0.700	0.967	0.908	0.912	0.853	0.935	0.863
M9	0.122	0.115	0.112	0.654	0.095	0.126	0.101	0.123	1.000	0.665	0.572	0.585	0.609	0.449	0.341
M10	0.995	0.797	0.735	0.651	0.511	0.739	0.743	0.845	0.122	1.000	0.934	0.935	0.920	0.933	0.810
M11	0.874	0.725	0.769	0.728	0.845	0.834	0.796	0.867	0.140	0.875	1.000	0.999	0.988	0.901	0.832
M12	0.877	0.711	0.770	0.728	0.845	0.830	0.794	0.868	0.138	0.881	0.999	1.000	0.987	0.900	0.830
M13	0.738	0.799	0.772	0.728	0.458	0.649	0.704	0.686	0.123	0.813	0.890	0.895	1.000	0.910	0.817
M14	0.884	0.871	0.743	0.692	0.875	0.729	0.843	0.880	0.118	0.884	0.850	0.851	0.851	1.000	0.913
M15	0.748	0.890	0.866	0.679	0.721	0.858	0.839	0.796	0.120	0.744	0.790	0.780	0.744	0.775	1.000

2.2 Experimental data summary

A large data set was collected for hydrocarbons of interest diluted in either O₂/N₂ or O₂/Ar (2727 points in total). The collected IDT range is from 2.6 μ s [151] up to 20.9 ms [152] (both points are for highly diluted propane/O₂/Ar mixture). The literature review showed that the highest pressure rise parameter dP/dt after shock wave reflection was 8.5%. Unfortunately, not all papers provided this parameter. According to Hanson and Davidson [108] the strongest influence of the facility effect was observed for IDTs higher than 1 ms, therefore it was arbitrarily decided to exclude from the analysis experimental points with an IDT longer than 1 ms. This operation excluded 233 points, which gave a final value of 2244 experimental points. Table 2.3 summarizes the experimental data conditions, which remained in the analysis.

Table 2.3. Database of ignition delay times from shock tube experiments used in the mechanism comparison. Temperature (T) and pressure (P) refer to the condition behind a reflected shock wave, and equivalence ratio Φ and dilution X_D (with either argon or nitrogen) to the condition in front of the shock wave.

Hydrocarbon	Oxydizer	References	No of points	T [K]	P [bar]	Φ [-]	X_D [%]
CH ₄	O ₂ /Ar	[153–167]	419	1089–2597	0.2–267.1	0.1–4	54.5–99.7
	O ₂ /N ₂		144	1041–1729	10.1–196.6	0.3–3	54.5–76.6
C ₂ H ₆	O ₂ /Ar	[153, 160, 154, 168, 156, 161, 162, 169, 170]	221	1126–2450	0.2–20.3	0.35–2	75–99.9
C ₂ H ₄	O ₂ /Ar	[151, 154, 155, 160, 171]	159	1102–2211	1.1–41.3	0.13–2	75–99
	O ₂ /N ₂		4	1073–1565	2.3–4.9	1	75
C ₂ H ₂	O ₂ /Ar	[172, 173]	160	1133–2094	1.2–1.9	0.06–2	89.4–98.6
C ₃ H ₈	O ₂ /Ar	[151, 174, 154, 155, 175, 162, 176–181]	305	1019–2170	1.1–68.3	0.13–2	75–99.7
	O ₂ /N ₂		34	1154–1510	3.4–23.9	0.99–1	75
C ₃ H ₆	O ₂ /Ar	[182]	111	1164–1756	1.5–48.1	0.5–2	75.5–95.6
	O ₂ /N ₂		89	1046–1422	9.4–47.6	0.5–2	72.3–85.3
n-C ₄ H ₁₀	O ₂ /Ar	[183, 154, 184]	41	1352–1734	1.1–4.2	0.5–2	85–96.3
	O ₂ /N ₂		68	995–1498	1–52.1	0.3–2	74.2–81.2
iso-C ₄ H ₁₀	O ₂ /Ar	[184, 154, 170]	68	1341–1864	1.5–13.9	0.25–2	92.5–99.9
	O ₂ /N ₂		52	998–1567	0.9–41.2	0.3–2	74.2–78.2
1-C ₄ H ₈	O ₂ /Ar	[18, 3]	72	1077–1835	1.3–18.7	0.5–2	87–96.5
	O ₂ /N ₂		18	921–1290	11–55.1	0.5–2	75.4–78
2-C ₄ H ₈	O ₂ /N ₂	[18]	60	965–1397	9.8–58.4	0.5–2	73.8–77.6
iso-C ₄ H ₈	O ₂ /Ar	[18, 6]	86	1103–1715	1.9–49.1	0.5–2	76.1–99
	O ₂ /N ₂		133	1018–1500	8.9–61.1	0.3–2	73.8–78.2

Experimental condition range and distribution are discussed to better visualize the first and the most important parameter influencing assessment of the mechanisms' performance - experimental input.

The validation process is more accurate when the number of high-quality points in a sample is high (Figure 2.1: Top) and the experimental range of conditions is wide (Figure 2.1: Middle & Bottom). The ratio of argon to nitrogen diluted mixtures is 1642/602. The highest number of points was found for methane (563) and most of these points (419) were obtained with argon as inert gas. The experimental temperature and pressure ranges covered here are the widest: 1041–2597 K and \sim 0.2–267.1 bar. The least investigated species was 2-butene with 60 points and with only nitrogen as inert gas.

In general, the experimental conditions of ignition delay times are not evenly distributed. As an example, in Figure 2.2 experimental conditions (temperature, pressure, dilution level and equivalence ratio) of iso-C₄H₈ are plotted on histograms presenting density of accumulated points. Iso-butene points cluster in 3 regions: $P \in (30; 60 \text{ bar})$ and $T \in (1000; 1400 \text{ K})$; $P \sim 10 \text{ bar}$ and $T \in (1100; 1600 \text{ K})$ and $P \sim 1 \text{ bar}$ and $T \in (1200; 1700 \text{ K})$. Additionally, after considering dilution ($X_D \simeq 75, 85, 95, 99\%$), equivalence ratio ($\Phi = 0.3, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0$) and inert gas, more than 20 clusters might be differentiated. The biggest density of points (dark blue) is noticeable for the temperature range from 1000 K to 1400 K, pressure 10 bar and inert gas fraction below 80%. Taking into account all parameters (P, T, Φ , inert gas and inert gas fraction) that describe experimental conditions, one may notice clusters of points making some conditions known better, while others provide little or no information. Hence, comprehensive assessment is possible in some regions only. Simultaneously, such plots highlight gaps in IDT data which might be useful for future research.

Figure 2.1. **Top:** Number of experimental IDTs accumulated for each mixture with regard to inert gas. **Middle & Bottom:** Comparison of pressure and temperature ranges of collected hydrocarbons (bar: wide, dark blue - argon, narrow, light blue - nitrogen).

Figure 2.2. 2D histogram of experimental ignition delay points number of iso-butene.

The authors took care to make use of only high temperature ignition and high quality data. In order to analyze the quality of experiments and their usefulness, the error distribution is analyzed across all experimental data sets. As a first step, ignition delay times are divided into uniform sets of fuel, reference, pressure, dilution range and inert gas. In total 156 sets are identified. Then, the mean of absolute error function E (MAE) is calculated for each data set and each mechanism, and the results are presented in box plots (e.g., Figure 2.3). A box indicates the distribution of mechanisms' MAE within one data set. It is decided to remove from the analysis experimental data sets which are outliers and which reproduced much more poorly than other sets within the same species.

However, consideration is given such that after exclusion the remaining experimental set is not considerably smaller. The assumption is that the quality of experimental data is reasonable if there are mechanisms able to reproduce them with a satisfactory level of accuracy. This level of accuracy differs between hydrocarbons and depends on relative reproduction of data sets. The method does not give a sharp indication, whether a data set should be removed.

Figure 2.3. MAE for C_2H_4 , C_2H_6 , C_3H_6 and $1-C_4H_8$ across experimental data sets N . Data sets are described in detail in Supplementary materials. The red dashed line indicates the median of MAE.

As an example, in Figure 2.3 box plots of MAE are presented for C_2H_4 , C_2H_6 , C_3H_6 and $1-C_4H_8$. For propene and iso-butene almost all data sets achieve a satisfactory match between a mechanism and experimental IDTs. Hence, none of them are excluded. In the case of ethene and ethane 130, 129, 128 and 32 data sets are reproduced more poorly than the rest - there are no mechanisms able to predict these IDTs accurately. Moreover, 130, 129, 128 sets come from the same source and it is reasonable to remove them together.

The same analysis is carried out for the rest of hydrocarbons and as a result, the following data sets are additionally removed: methane - 70, 104, 62, 44, 19; propane - 144. In total 101 points are excluded.

2.3 Calculations

Ignition delay times are calculated utilizing a constant volume explosion model with adaptive time step in Cantera 2.2.1. [185] in the Matlab R2016a environment. The relative and absolute tolerances were set at 1.0E-09 and 1.0E-20, respectively. Recently, Langer et al. [186] summarized that Cantera, Chemkin-Pro, FlameMaster and OpenSMOKE++ predict consistent results for homogenous, isochoric, adiabatic batch reactors. The main advantage of Cantera is that it is free open-source software enabling high-fidelity computations for the wider community. By these means, in simulations, dP/dt is equal to 0. Initial conditions for calculations are: experimental temperature (T_5) and experimental pressure (P_5) behind a reflected shock wave and composition of the investigated mixture. To speed up calculations and make sure that only high temperature ignition was taken into account, the calculations were terminated when the temperature increase exceeded 95% of the difference between adiabatic flame temperature and initial temperature. Ignition delay times in the literature were determined with the use of 6 definitions of IDTs (maximum gradient of pressure, maximum of OH^* , maximum of CH^* , 50% of maximum of OH^* and tangential methods of pressure and OH^*). All methods were implemented into Cantera script to keep consistency in comparison. If the definition was not stated in the papers, the maximum gradient of pressure was used.

OH^* and CH^* based definitions

Similar to Olm et al. [113], if an IDT definition could not be modeled, another similar definition was used. Thereby, ignition definitions based on calculations of OH^* and CH^* profiles were replaced by calculations of OH and CH, in the case of mechanisms that do not contain OH^* and CH^* . The Author's intention was to utilize mechanisms as they were published. Hence, the original mechanisms have not been extended by reaction blocks for the calculation of OH^* and CH^* . However, a brief study using Aramco Mech 2.0 is performed to account for inaccuracy arising from this approach.

Exemplary ignition delay times are calculated with definitions based on both OH and OH*, and temperature profile (max gradient temperature, tangential OH, max OH, tangential OH* and max OH*). Then relative differences between OH and OH* definitions are assessed with respect to definition based on temperature profile:

$$\epsilon = \frac{\tau_{OH} - \tau_{OH^*}}{\tau_T}. \quad (2.2)$$

Mixture of 1% iso-butane + 4.5% oxygen + 95.5% argon is used as an example. Calculated temperature and pressure ranges were: 900–1900 K and 1–50 bar.

Table 2.4. Performance of DNN model and DRMs for nitrogen diluted mixtures only.

Max OH*						
ϵ	900 K	1000 K	1100 K	1200 K	1300 K	1900 K
1 bar	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.24%	2.60%	10.67%
5 bar	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%	0.37%	2.29%
20 bar	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.14%	1.21%
50 bar	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.04%	0.71%

Tangential OH*						
ϵ	900 K	1000 K	1100 K	1200 K	1300 K	1900 K
1 bar	0.00%	0.00%	0.03%	0.26%	1.45%	5.02%
5 bar	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.07%	0.41%	1.47%
20 bar	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.06%	0.46%	1.68%
50 bar	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.07%	0.52%	1.84%

Results of calculations are presented in Table 2.4. The difference between definition based on OH and OH* increase with increasing temperature and decreasing pressure, thereby when IDT is the shortest. Hence, the highest values are for 1 bar and 1900 K: 10.67% for max OH* and 5.02% for tangential OH*. Both differences are smaller than experimental overall uncertainty. In the present work experimental IDTs defined using either OH* or CH* lie in a pressure range of 1–48 bar and a temperature range of 1046–1890 K. Hence, replacement of OH* and CH* definitions by OH and CH based definition have not introduced a significant error in the analysis. It is assumed that these conclusions apply to other species.

2.3.1 Validation approach

The performance of the mechanisms is assessed at different levels of generality. At the first level, the following error function E is defined:

$$E = \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \cdot \epsilon \right) \quad (2.3)$$

$$\epsilon = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } |\tau_{sim} - \tau_{exp}| < g \\ \frac{(\tau_{sim} - \tau_{exp}) - g}{\tau_{exp}} & \text{if } \tau_{sim} - \tau_{exp} > g \\ \frac{(\tau_{sim} - \tau_{exp}) + g}{\tau_{exp}} & \text{if } \tau_{sim} - \tau_{exp} < -g \end{cases} \quad (2.4)$$

where τ_{sim} and τ_{exp} are simulated and experimental IDTs, respectively, and g is experimental overall uncertainty in ignition delay time. The overall uncertainty g includes uncertainties in assessment of reflected shock conditions (pressure, temperature, mixture composition) and uncertainty in determination of IDT by measured signals. The overall uncertainty g in collected IDTs ranges from $\pm 10\%$ (e.g. in 1-C₄H₈ data from [3]) to $\pm 20\%$ (e.g. in C₃H₆ data from [14]). If the overall uncertainty is not stated in the data source, the assumption $g = \pm 20\%$ is made. The function ϵ is the relative error reduced by the overall experimental uncertainty. Hence, if the difference between the measured and computed value is smaller than the uncertainty, the function ϵ takes 0 and it is acceptable to say there is a perfect match between an experiment and mechanism's prediction.

The erf function is defined as follows:

$$\operatorname{erf}(x) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x \exp -t^2 dt \quad (2.5)$$

The E function brings ϵ to a range from -1 to 1 so that it facilitates the comparison and presentation of results. Moreover, the function $\operatorname{erf}(x \cdot \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\pi})$ has its slope equal to 1 at the origin. Therefore, for lower error values, ϵ can be approximated by E (for $|E| < 0.3$ the error of approximation is $|\epsilon - E| < 0.01$). The DRM which computes the IDT best gives the error function E a value close to zero.

In the next step, each set of E values obtained for a particular fuel and a detailed reaction mechanism is divided into ranges of similar initial parameters. Temperature divisions come every 250 K. Equivalence ratio Φ is split into lean, near stoichiometric ($0.9 < \Phi < 1.1$) and rich. Division of pressure differs between species. The scatter of the E values is shown in box-whisker plots within created ranges of P , T and Φ , separately (e.g., Figure 2.4). A black dot inside a white circle indicates the median of the error function (\bar{E}). Bottom and top edges of the box indicate the 25th and 75th percentiles, respectively. The whiskers extend to the most extreme data points after the exclusion of outliers. Outliers are defined as values which are 1.5 times the interquartile range away from the top or bottom of the box, and are displayed with a red + sign. The box plots give information on statistical dispersion of the error function E . A good mechanism will have: firstly, median of error function (\bar{E}) close to 0; secondly, narrow IQR; thirdly, narrow whiskers and, fourthly, few or no outliers close to 0. In addition to the box-whisker plots, a plot summarizing the number of points in each range is shown, as latter parameters (M) are the weighted average of errors, where the weights are the number of points in each range. Hence, the plot may help facilitate the comparison and elaborate on the results.

Secondly, absolute medians of the error value ($|\bar{E}|$) are presented on heat maps of pressure against temperature (e.g., Figure 2.5). Dark red indicates higher $|\bar{E}|$, green color denotes $|\bar{E}|=0$. The heat maps consist of 20x20 elements and the $|\bar{E}|$ value is calculated within each element. The envelope is minimum and maximum values of pressure and temperature of experimental IDTs of a given species. The heat maps provide more insight into the performance of mechanisms, particularly at the lowest errors. They report on performance of a mechanism that is not uniform (higher or lower than indicated by the global error function), whether locally there are still mechanisms with lower $|\bar{E}|$ and whether $|\bar{E}|$ is correlated more with either temperature or pressure.

Figure 2.4. Box graphs of the error function E for $C_2H_4/O_2/Ar$. **Row I:** temperature, **Row II:** pressure, **Row III:** equivalence ratio (ranges are given above the graphs).

Figure 2.5. Pressure-temperature heat maps with $|\bar{E}|$ (absolute \bar{E}) values comparing performance of M10, M8 and M2 mechanisms for propene mixtures (both argon and nitrogen diluted).

Thirdly, to assess each mechanism quantitatively another parameter, the M function, is introduced:

$$M = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_r} |\bar{E}| \cdot w_i}{w} \quad (2.6)$$

where \bar{E} is the median of error function (E) in particular initial parameter range (same ranges as in box-whisker plots), N_r - number of ranges of a given parameter, w_i - number of points in i th range, w - total number of points. Therefore, the M parameter represents the weighted average of absolute values of medians. By these means the detailed reaction mechanism with the best performance should have $|\bar{E}|$ values as low as possible for as many ranges as possible and as a result the lowest M value. As the median values were calculated within the same data set, but divided by means of initial temperature, pressure or equivalence ratio, the M function is distinguished as three types: $M(P)$, $M(T)$ and $M(\Phi)$, plus additionally, the average of these three, \tilde{M} .

2.4 Results

2.4.1 Methane

Methane is one of the most examined fuels. Literature review of its IDTs covered 15 publications [153–167] giving in total 563 points (419 for argon and 144 for nitrogen). After the exclusion of five datasets (70, 104, 62, 44, 19) 495 points remained in the analysis (384 for argon and 111 for nitrogen). The majority of these points cluster in one apparent region (dark blue color in Figure 2.6): highly diluted, stoichiometric mixtures at low pressure and around 1500–1700 K.

Figure 2.6. 2D histogram of experimental ignition delay points number of methane.

In Table 2.5 M parameters are summarized. M14 and M2 result in the lowest \tilde{M} in the case of argon as inert gas. \tilde{M} of 0.000 and 0.001 indicate that there is a perfect match between computations and experiments. It can be seen in Figure 2.8 that the main difference in performance of M14 and M2 is for 1250–1749 K and 10–49.6 bar, where M14 performs slightly better, which is also noticeable in the heat maps in Figure 2.7. In the temperature box graphs a change in trend is noticeable: the lowest temperature range mechanisms tend to overestimate IDTs, while the highest tend to underestimate IDTs. This might be evidence of incorrectly predicted activation energy. If nitrogen is concerned, M2 together with M7 and M8 give the lowest \tilde{M} . For a temperature range of 1506–1729

K, M12, M13, M15 and M6 give narrower scatter of errors, hence they may locally be a better choice. The M2 mechanism is the best across the two inert gases.

Table 2.5. Comparison of M values calculated for $\text{CH}_4/\text{O}_2/\text{Ar}$ (top) and $\text{CH}_4/\text{O}_2/\text{N}_2$ (bottom) mixtures. Values in bold denote the lowest M values.

CH_4, Ar	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M12	M13	M14	M15
$M(T)$	0.002	0.052	0.021	0.156	0.054	0.027	0.070		0.088	0.157	0.154	0.000	0.052
$M(P)$	0.000	0.050	0.011	0.170	0.044	0.026	0.063		0.080	0.120	0.121	0.001	0.052
$M(\Phi)$	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.177	0.000	0.000	0.016		0.035	0.063	0.063	0.000	0.000
\tilde{M}	0.001	0.034	0.011	0.168	0.033	0.018	0.050		0.068	0.113	0.112	0.000	0.035

CH_4, N_2	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M12	M13	M14	M15
$M(T)$	0.000	0.176	0.145	0.294	0.173	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.020	0.014	0.053	0.175
$M(P)$	0.000	0.225	0.127	0.284	0.187	0.017	0.012		0.027	0.060	0.061	0.061	0.219
$M(\Phi)$	0.000	0.159	0.079	0.304	0.108	0.003	0.008		0.009	0.010	0.011	0.032	0.152
\tilde{M}	0.000	0.187	0.117	0.294	0.156	0.006	0.007		0.012	0.030	0.029	0.049	0.182

Figure 2.7. Pressure-temperature heat maps with $|\bar{E}|$ (absolute \bar{E}) values comparing performance of M2, M14 and M7 mechanisms for methane mixtures (both argon and nitrogen diluted).

Figure 2.8. Box graphs of the error function E for $\text{CH}_4/\text{O}_2/\text{Ar}$. **Row I:** temperature, **Row II:** pressure, **Row III:** equivalence ratio (ranges are given above the graphs).

2.4.2 Ethane

Literature review of ethane IDTs covered 9 papers [153, 160, 154, 168, 156, 161, 162, 169, 170] giving in total 221 points for argon only. The number dropped to 203 after exclusion of data set 32. The densest cluster of points is present for highly diluted stoichiometric mixtures in the lowest pressure and temperature region. In Table 2.6 the M parameters are summarized. The lowest \tilde{M} is reached by the M5 mechanism, followed by M7 and M3. The M parameters are as low as 0.000–0.003, what indicates that ethane IDTs can be reproduced very accurately. However, in the heat maps in Figure 2.9 a dark red spot at around 1250 K and 1 bar can be noticed for the three mechanisms.

Table 2.6. Comparison of M values calculated for $C_2H_6/O_2/Ar$ mixtures. Values in bold denote the lowest M values.

C_2H_6, Ar	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M12	M13	M14	M15
$M(T)$	0.017	0.029	0.123	0.004	0.157	0.023	0.019			0.088	0.090	0.002	0.281
$M(P)$	0.052	0.003	0.187	0.005	0.151	0.001	0.061			0.080	0.082	0.046	0.291
$M(\Phi)$	0.013	0.000	0.005	0.000	0.156	0.000	0.000			0.046	0.047	0.000	0.285
\tilde{M}	0.027	0.011	0.105	0.003	0.154	0.008	0.027			0.071	0.073	0.016	0.285

Figure 2.9. Pressure-temperature heat maps with $|\bar{E}|$ (absolute \bar{E}) values comparing performance of M5, M7 and M14 mechanisms for ethane mixtures (both argon and nitrogen diluted).

2.4.3 Ethene

Experimental IDTs of ethene presented in this Chapter come from 4 publications. In total 151 experimental IDTs for ethene (all for argon) are used in the analysis after the exclusion of data sets 130, 129, 128 as described above. A high number of points is accumulated at 3 bar and from 1000 to 1800 K with different Φ and dilution levels.

Table 2.7. Comparison of M values calculated for $C_2H_4/O_2/Ar$ mixtures. Values in bold denote the lowest M values.

C_2H_4, Ar	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M12	M13	M14	M15
$M(T)$	0.063	0.538	0.297	0.291	0.143	0.112	0.154	0.062	0.051	0.244	0.246	0.079	0.143
$M(P)$	0.051	0.607	0.275	0.312	0.123	0.037	0.084	0.082	0.078	0.175	0.177	0.103	0.026
$M(\Phi)$	0.083	0.764	0.119	0.407	0.123	0.280	0.038	0.058	0.055	0.206	0.209	0.071	0.295
\tilde{M}	0.065	0.637	0.231	0.337	0.130	0.143	0.092	0.067	0.061	0.209	0.211	0.084	0.155

Figure 2.10. Pressure-temperature heat maps of $|\bar{E}|$ values comparing performance of M10, M8 and M2 mechanisms for ethene.

Table 2.7 summarizes M values for ethene. The lowest \tilde{M} value for argon diluted mixtures (0.051) is obtained by mechanism M10 (NUIG n-Heptane). The second is M9 (NUIG n-Hexane) and the third M2 (CaltechMech). Figure 2.4 presents box graphs for $C_2H_4/O_2/Ar$. Analyzing the temperature box graph, the middle range has the highest number of points, hence it has the strongest influence on $M(T)$. The best mechanisms ($\bar{E}=0$) in this range are M2, M8, M9 (NUIG n-Hexane) and M10 (M15 has a wide interquartile range). In a temperature range of 1126–1246 K M14 and M2 are more accurate than M10 with $\bar{E}=0$. In the highest temperature range M14 is the most accurate, together with M5, although M5 has a high scatter of error, resulting in a wide IQR. In this range many mechanisms tend to underestimate IDTs. The lowest pressures of 1.1–4 bar consists of the highest number of IDTs (in total 120 points), therefore strongly influencing $M(P)$. In this range M2, M8, M9 and M10 are the most precise. In the next range (12.2–16.6 bar) very good performance can be seen with M2, M12, M13 and M14. The range of 39.6–41.3 bar consists of 6 points only. M10 has the worst performance. M2 and M14 have $\bar{E}=0$. All mechanisms have a tendency to underestimate ignition delay times of

mixtures with Φ equal to 2. Figure 2.10 presents a heat map - a comparison of $|\bar{E}|$ maps on a P-T plot for M10, M8 and M2 mechanisms. In that manner, it is clear that although M10 has the lowest \tilde{M} , mechanism M2 has a lower $|\bar{E}|$ value when pressure is above 10 bar. M8 appears to be slightly more accurate than M10 when pressure is below 5 bar. Again, two important aspects are noticeable – assessment of mechanism performance is a multivariate problem and distribution of ethene experimental points is sparse, which makes validation possible only in some regions.

2.4.4 Acetylene

Hidaka et al. [172] and Eiteneer and Frenklach [173] measured acetylene ignition delay times in a shock tube in 1996 and in 2003, respectively. 160 experimental points with a narrow pressure range (1–2 bar) and argon as inert gas are utilized in the assessment (133 points in [172] and 27 in [173]). The temperature range of these points is 1133–2094 K, Φ is 0.06–2 and dilution from 89.4 to 98.6% (Table 2.3). Most of the points are accumulated in the range 1.2–1.3 bar.

Table 2.8. Comparison of M values calculated for $C_2H_2/O_2/Ar$ mixtures. Values in bold denote the lowest M values.

C_2H_2, Ar	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M12	M13	M14	M15
$M(T)$	0.000	0.373	0.618	0.206	0.000	0.016	0.010	0.009	0.009	0.128	0.128	0.000	0.001
$M(P)$	0.000	0.228	0.629	0.206	0.000	0.011	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.103	0.102	0.000	0.000
$M(\Phi)$	0.000	0.375	0.598	0.192	0.000	0.021	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.114	0.115	0.000	0.000
\tilde{M}	0.000	0.326	0.615	0.201	0.000	0.016	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.115	0.115	0.000	0.000

Table 2.8 summarizes M values for $C_2H_2/O_2/Ar$. Seven of 13 mechanisms are identified by \tilde{M} and M parameters lower than 0.010. In Figure 2.11 it can be seen that although in many cases the median of mechanism error is equal to 0, a high number of outliers is apparent. Polimi mechanisms (M12, M13) tend to underestimate IDTs with respect to temperature and equivalence ratio.

In Figure 2.12 error heat maps are presented for M2, M6 and M14. Although all three mechanisms reached \tilde{M} and M equal to 0, differences in performance are noticeable. M2 is more accurate than M6 and M14 and its performance is more uniform across pressure and temperature ranges.

Recently, Lokachari et al. [187] showed that AramcoMech 2.0 (which gives the same results as M10, NUIG n-Heptane) and other mechanisms analyzed in that paper cannot accurately predict IDTs at 10, 20 and 30 bar. They concluded that more work is needed to better understand acetylene oxidation. It has to be noted that the good performance presented in the present chapter might be true for ~ 2 bar only.

Figure 2.11. Box graphs of the error function E for $C_2H_2/O_2/Ar$. **Row I**: temperature, **Row II**: pressure, **Row III**: equivalence ratio (ranges are given above the graphs).

Figure 2.12. Pressure-temperature heat maps of $|\bar{E}|$ values comparing performance of M2, M6 and M14 mechanisms for ethene.

2.4.5 Propane

Figure 2.13. 2D histogram of experimental ignition delay points number of propane.

Propane IDTs were found in 12 papers [151, 174, 154, 155, 175, 162, 176–181]. After exclusion of IDTs longer than 1 ms and one data set (144) 335 points remained in the analysis (305 for argon and 30 for nitrogen). Argon diluted mixtures have a wide temperature range from 1019 up to 2170 K, and a pressure range 1–68 bar, whereas nitrogen mixtures reach lower temperatures of 1154–1510 K, and pressures up to 23.9 bar (Table 2.3). Argon molar fraction varies from 75 up to 99.7 %. Nitrogen fraction is around 75%. Hence, all nitrogen points are for stoichiometric propane-air mixtures. Many of these points cluster around 1400 K and below 10 bar at 6 dilution levels. Equivalence

ratios of 1, 0.5 and 2 were the most examined.

Table 2.9. Comparison of M values calculated for $C_3H_8/O_2/Ar$ (top) and $C_3H_8/O_2/N_2$ (bottom) mixtures. Values in bold denote the lowest M values.

C_3H_8, Ar	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M12	M13	M14	M15
$M(T)$	0.067	0.082	0.113	0.266	0.000	0.000	0.083		0.021	0.203	0.253	0.000	0.050
$M(P)$	0.025	0.039	0.048	0.289	0.000	0.000	0.048		0.024	0.214	0.255	0.000	0.020
$M(\Phi)$	0.000	0.095	0.025	0.265	0.000	0.000	0.033		0.001	0.206	0.256	0.000	0.000
\tilde{M}	0.031	0.072	0.062	0.273	0.000	0.000	0.055		0.015	0.208	0.255	0.000	0.023

C_3H_8, N_2	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M12	M13	M14	M15
$M(T)$	0.786	0.657	0.944	0.072	0.150	0.274	0.301		0.299	0.068	0.144	0.274	0.551
$M(P)$	0.840	0.646	0.921	0.088	0.073	0.144	0.192		0.211	0.070	0.160	0.195	0.564
$M(\Phi)$	0.893	0.647	1.000	0.069	0.067	0.065	0.171		0.211	0.064	0.160	0.182	0.548
\tilde{M}	0.840	0.650	0.955	0.076	0.096	0.161	0.221		0.240	0.067	0.154	0.217	0.554

In the case of argon, three of the investigated mechanisms result in M values equal to 0: M6, M7 and M14. In box graphs it can be seen that they have narrow IQRs and M6 together with M14 have a slightly smaller scatter of outliers. Propane-air IDTs are modeled the most accurately by M12, according to the M values. In Figure 2.14 M6, M7 and M12 mechanisms are compared using pressure-temperature heat maps. Indeed, the differences between M6 and M7 are very minimal. Five dark red spots are noticeable in the case of the two mechanisms. Three of these spots are much better reproduced by M12.

Figure 2.14. Pressure-temperature heat maps with $|\bar{E}|$ (absolute \bar{E}) values comparing performance of M6, M7 and M12 mechanisms for propane mixtures (both argon and nitrogen diluted).

Figure 2.15. Box graphs of the error function E for $C_3H_8/O_2/Ar$. **Row I:** temperature, **Row II:** pressure, **Row III:** equivalence ratio (ranges are given above the graphs).

2.4.6 Propene

Propene ignition delay times were investigated by Burke et al. [14] in 2015. In total 261 points were collected, but only 200 remained after excluding IDTs longer than 1 ms: 111 points of argon diluted and 89 of nitrogen diluted (Table 2.1). The points cluster at 2 pressure levels for nitrogen (~ 10 and 40 bar) and 4 levels for argon ($\sim 1-2$, 5, 10 and 40 bar). The temperature range of $C_3H_6/O_2/N_2$ is narrower and reaches lower values than $C_3H_6/O_2/Ar$ (1046–1422 K versus 1164–1756 K).

Table 2.10. Comparison of M values calculated for $C_3H_6/O_2/Ar$ and $C_3H_6/O_2/N_2$ mixtures. Values in bold denote the lowest M values.

C_3H_6, Ar	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M12	M13	M14	M15
$M(T)$	0.061	0.212		0.416	0.156	0.126	0.017	0.621	0.013	0.122	0.248	0.236	0.198
$M(P)$	0.073	0.200		0.415	0.154	0.126	0.035	0.750	0.000	0.115	0.240	0.254	0.196
$M(\Phi)$	0.053	0.220		0.418	0.152	0.076	0.019	0.761	0.000	0.123	0.251	0.228	0.206
\tilde{M}	0.062	0.211		0.416	0.154	0.109	0.024	0.711	0.004	0.120	0.246	0.239	0.200

C_3H_6, N_2	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M12	M13	M14	M15
$M(T)$	0.365	0.398		0.371	0.344	0.163	0.039	0.217	0.000	0.036	0.169	0.288	0.409
$M(P)$	0.370	0.400		0.368	0.346	0.230	0.039	0.139	0.000	0.038	0.176	0.295	0.414
$M(\Phi)$	0.360	0.412		0.364	0.344	0.129	0.015	0.166	0.000	0.074	0.171	0.297	0.423
\tilde{M}	0.365	0.403		0.368	0.344	0.174	0.031	0.174	0.000	0.049	0.172	0.293	0.415

The relative performance of the mechanisms for $C_3H_6/O_2/Ar$ and $C_3H_6/O_2/N_2$ is similar, as shown in Table 2.10. M10 (NUIG n-Heptane) has the lowest \tilde{M} . The second mechanism is M8 (NUIG Pentane). M2 (CaltechMech) is very accurate in the case of $C_3H_6/O_2/Ar$, but for $C_3H_6/O_2/N_2$ it has one of the worst performances. It is clear from Figure 2.16 that M2 performance below 1500 K is similar across both mixtures, but in the case of argon where the temperature range extends up to 1756 K its performance improves as the temperature rises. Performance of M2 is correlated with temperature rather than with the type of inert gas.

Figure 2.5 presents heat maps for M10, M8 and M2. Gradual improvement of M2 with temperature is visible. M10 has uniform accuracy across temperature and pressure, but locally (above ~ 1500 K) M8 and M2 result in lower error.

Figure 2.16. Temperature box graphs of error function E for (top) $C_3H_6/O_2/Ar$ and (bottom) $C_3H_6/O_2/N_2$. (ranges are given above the graphs).

2.4.7 Butane isomers

Butane IDTs were found in 5 papers [184, 154, 170, 183, 154]. After exclusion of IDTs longer than 1 ms, 109 points for n-butane (Ar/N₂: 41/68) and 120 points for iso-butane (Ar/N₂: 68/52) remained in the analysis. IDTs of mixtures diluted in argon were collected at higher temperatures (n/iso: 1352/1341–1734/1864 K) and lower pressures (n/iso: 1.1/1.5–4.2/13.9 bar) than those diluted in nitrogen (n/iso: 995/998–1498/1567 K and 1/0.9–52.1/41.2 bar). Dilution in argon is higher than in nitrogen (Table 2.3).

Table 2.11. Comparison of M values calculated for iso-butane and n-butane. Values in bold denote the lowest M values.

iso-, N ₂	M6	M7	M8	M10	M13	n-, N ₂	M6	M7	M8	M10	M13
$M(T)$	0.030	0.064	0.000	0.000	0.009	$M(T)$	0.024	0.068	0.000	0.043	0.114
$M(P)$	0.091	0.146	0.010	0.000	0.033	$M(P)$	0.035	0.088	0.010	0.097	0.107
$M(\Phi)$	0.002	0.108	0.000	0.000	0.037	$M(\Phi)$	0.005	0.088	0.003	0.021	0.009
\tilde{M}	0.041	0.106	0.003	0.000	0.026	\tilde{M}	0.021	0.081	0.004	0.054	0.077

iso-, Ar	M6	M7	M8	M10	M13	n-, Ar	M6	M7	M8	M10	M13
$M(T)$	0.031	0.000	0.265	0.042	0.321	$M(T)$	0.000	0.012	0.000	0.000	0.464
$M(P)$	0.000	0.001	0.253	0.041	0.262	$M(P)$	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.454
$M(\Phi)$	0.000	0.001	0.308	0.063	0.318	$M(\Phi)$	0.000	0.031	0.000	0.000	0.460
\tilde{M}	0.010	0.001	0.276	0.049	0.300	\tilde{M}	0.000	0.014	0.000	0.000	0.459

Figure 2.17. Pressure-temperature heat maps with $|\bar{E}|$ (absolute \bar{E}) values comparing performance of M7, M8 and M10 mechanisms for n-butane (top) and iso-butane (bottom) mixtures (both argon and nitrogen diluted).

In Table 2.11 M parameters are summarized and the lowest values are denoted in bold. The most accurate mechanisms are: iso-butane/ O_2/N_2 - M10 and M8, iso-butane/ O_2/Ar - M7 and M6, n-butane/ O_2/N_2 - M8 and M6, and n-butane/ O_2/Ar - M6, M8, and M10. The difference in DRMs' performance between nitrogen and argon may arise from noticeably different temperature ranges. In Figure 2.17 M7, M8 and M10 are compared using pressure-temperature heat maps. In the case of the M8 mechanism for iso-butane worse accuracy is apparent for higher temperatures. M10 and M7 reproduce IDTs of both iso- and n-butane across all ranges of pressure, temperature and inert gas very well.

2.4.8 Butene isomers

Experimental data on ignition delay times of butene were found for 3 isomers: 1-C₄H₈, 2-C₄H₈ and iso-C₄H₈ (Table 2.3). 2-butene is not differentiated into cis- and trans-2-butene, as Li et al. reported in [18] that they measured their IDTs as identical. After exclusion of IDT longer than 1 ms, 90 IDTs of 1-C₄H₈, 60 of 2-C₄H₈ and 219 of iso-C₄H₈ remained in the analysis.

Table 2.12. Comparison of M values calculated for butene isomers. Values in bold denote the lowest M values.

1-C ₄ H ₈ , Ar	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M12	M13	M14	M15
$M(T)$				0.654	0.224	0.256	0.164		0.059		0.070		0.162
$M(P)$				0.645	0.128	0.222	0.129		0.006		0.044		0.093
$M(\Phi)$				0.665	0.076	0.228	0.059		0.033		0.092		0.024
\tilde{M}				0.655	0.142	0.236	0.118		0.033		0.068		0.093
1-C ₄ H ₈ , N ₂	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M12	M13	M14	M15
$M(T)$				0.217	1.000	0.630	0.429		0.008		0.017		1.000
$M(P)$				0.329	0.963	0.558	0.225		0.051		0.027		0.990
$M(\Phi)$				0.329	0.963	0.558	0.225		0.051		0.027		0.990
\tilde{M}				0.291	0.975	0.582	0.293		0.037		0.024		0.993
2-C ₄ H ₈ , N ₂	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M12	M13	M14	M15
$M(T)$				0.870	0.732	0.965	0.062	0.000	0.036		0.333		
$M(P)$				0.751	0.614	0.971	0.068	0.000	0.030		0.337		
$M(\Phi)$				0.986	0.592	0.969	0.054	0.000	0.071		0.346		
\tilde{M}				0.869	0.646	0.968	0.061	0.000	0.046		0.339		
iso-C ₄ H ₈ , Ar	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M12	M13	M14	M15
$M(T)$	0.248				0.317	0.288	0.064		0.077		0.238		
$M(P)$	0.244				0.339	0.296	0.006		0.064		0.224		
$M(\Phi)$	0.230				0.207	0.309	0.016		0.057		0.239		
\tilde{M}	0.240				0.288	0.297	0.029		0.066		0.233		
iso-C ₄ H ₈ , N ₂	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M12	M13	M14	M15
$M(T)$	0.448				0.970	0.198	0.000		0.000		0.137		
$M(P)$	0.445				0.945	0.161	0.000		0.000		0.127		
$M(\Phi)$	0.452				1.000	0.382	0.000		0.000		0.138		
\tilde{M}	0.448				0.972	0.247	0.000		0.000		0.134		

The M values are summarized in Table 2.12. M10 (NUIG n-Heptane) and M13 (Polimi PRF PAH LT) have the lowest \tilde{M} for 1-butene, whereas M8–M10 (NUIG mechanisms) are the lowest for 2- and iso-butenes. Mechanism M10 is one of the most accurate for all three isomers of butene. Heat maps presenting $|\bar{E}|$ of mechanism M10 across 1-, 2- and

iso-butenes are shown in Figure 2.18. Of note: M15 (USC Mech II) switched from being an accurate mechanism for 1-C₄H₈/O₂/Ar to poor performance in the case of 1-C₄H₈/O₂/N₂. The reason is the different temperature range between inert gases – for argon 1077–1835 K, for nitrogen 921–1290 K, hence the much better performance in the case of the argon diluted mixture is caused by the fact that M15 is a high temperature mechanism.

Figure 2.18. Pressure-temperature heat maps with $|\bar{E}|$ (absolute \bar{E}) values presenting performance of M10 mechanism for 1-, 2- and iso-butenes.

2.5 Conclusions

This chapter presents a comprehensive comparison of the performance of various DRMs in predicting the ignition delay times measured in a shock tube for C1–C4 alkanes, alkenes and acetylene. The analysis performed may be used as guidance for optimal choice of a detailed chemical kinetic mechanism to simulate combustion phenomena involving self-ignition and detonation. The comparison is presented at different levels of generality. Table 2.13 provides an indication of the overall performance of a kinetic mechanism characterized by the error function \tilde{M} . That gives general guidance as to which mechanism performs best across all investigated conditions, which differed strongly between mixtures. The overall range of conditions of all hydrocarbons was: temperature from 965 to 2597 K, pressure 0.2–267.1 bar, equivalence ratio 0.06–4.0 and inert gas dilution from 54.5% to 99.9% with either nitrogen or argon. Therefore, the function \tilde{M} is the average of the M functions calculated across temperature ($M(T)$), pressure ($M(P)$) and equivalence ratio ($M(\Phi)$).

More detailed information is provided by the heat maps where the absolute median of error function E is shown to visualize the error of the calculated parameter for a specific pressure and temperature. The heat maps provide more insight into the performance of mechanisms with the lowest error and inform about the performance non-uniformity – higher or lower than indicated by the global error function. By these means it is possible that some DRMs might perform better within a limited set of conditions than *the best* one as defined by the M error function. Additionally, analysis with the use of box plots was carried out. The statistical dispersion of the error function E is shown by interquartile range, median and outliers for conditions split into smaller ranges.

Table 2.13. Summary of the \tilde{M} parameter of all investigated mixtures and mechanisms (colors: green: $\tilde{M} = 0$; yellow: $\tilde{M} = 0.05$; white: $\tilde{M} = 0.3$).

Mixture		M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M12	M13	M14	M15
CH ₄	O ₂ /Ar	0.001	0.034	0.011	0.168	0.033	0.018	0.050		0.068	0.113	0.112	0.000	0.035
	O ₂ /N ₂	0.000	0.187	0.117	0.294	0.156	0.006	0.007		0.012	0.030	0.029	0.049	0.182
C ₂ H ₆	O ₂ /Ar	0.027	0.011	0.105	0.003	0.154	0.008	0.027			0.071	0.073	0.016	0.285
C ₂ H ₄	O ₂ /Ar	0.065	0.637	0.231	0.337	0.130	0.143	0.092	0.067	0.061	0.209	0.211	0.084	0.155
C ₂ H ₂	O ₂ /Ar	0.000	0.326	0.615	0.201	0.000	0.016	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.115	0.115	0.000	0.000
C ₃ H ₈	O ₂ /Ar	0.031	0.072	0.062	0.273	0.000	0.000	0.055		0.015	0.208	0.255	0.000	0.023
	O ₂ /N ₂	0.840	0.650	0.955	0.076	0.096	0.161	0.221		0.240	0.067	0.154	0.217	0.554
C ₃ H ₆	O ₂ /Ar	0.062	0.211		0.416	0.154	0.109	0.024	0.711	0.004	0.120	0.246	0.239	0.200
	O ₂ /N ₂	0.365	0.403		0.368	0.344	0.174	0.031	0.174	0.000	0.049	0.172	0.293	0.415
iso-C ₄ H ₁₀	O ₂ /Ar					0.010	0.001	0.276		0.049			0.300	
	O ₂ /N ₂					0.041	0.106	0.003		0.000		0.026		
n-C ₄ H ₁₀	O ₂ /Ar					0.000	0.014	0.000		0.000			0.459	
	O ₂ /N ₂					0.021	0.081	0.004		0.054		0.077		
iso-C ₄ H ₈	O ₂ /Ar	0.240				0.288	0.297	0.029		0.066		0.233		
	O ₂ /N ₂	0.448				0.972	0.247	0.000		0.000		0.134		
1-C ₄ H ₈	O ₂ /Ar				0.655	0.142	0.236	0.118	0.000	0.033		0.068		0.093
	O ₂ /N ₂				0.291	0.975	0.582	0.293		0.037		0.024		0.993
2-C ₄ H ₈	O ₂ /N ₂				0.869	0.646	0.968	0.061	0.000	0.046		0.339		

Additional comment should be devoted to the experimental sets and selection of mechanisms. Although 10 data sets (101 point in total) were excluded from the analysis based on the approach taken and the Author took only high temperature ignition data into account, some of the other experimental sets may present systemic facility errors. The calculations of ignition delay time performed for this dissertation did not account for facility effects (dP/dt), because not all references provided dP/dt values. Hence, ignition delay times longer than 1 ms were excluded from analysis and the assumption of negligible influence on ignition delays was made. In the end, 15 mechanisms were addressed in the present Chapter. Based on calculations of the Pearson linear correlation coefficient

two were excluded (AramcoMech 2.0 and Polimi C1C3 LT HT 1412). Many of these mechanisms have not been particularly developed for species addressed in the present chapter. Some of the species are included in the mechanisms simply because they are intermediate species, for which it appears that no study has been specifically developed to study their ignition.

Special attention is required, as the quality of mapping of other properties such as laminar burning velocity has not been checked. Another difficulty in optimal selection of kinetic mechanism is the sparsity in distribution of experimental points in the condition matrix. Points are not evenly distributed over the investigated range and the measured experimental points are usually clustered together within certain conditions of limited ranges of temperature, pressure, and equivalence ratio. Additionally, as was remarked by Bernardi et al. in [120], this kind of comparison has certain limitations and does not indicate the absolute level of agreement achieved between simulations and experiments, i.e., regarding the shape of IDT against temperature. In many applications the reproduction of the first derivative of IDT vs T may be more important than an absolute value, e.g., in CFD while analyzing the influence of temperature using a case already calibrated for a base condition.

Chapter 3

Ignition delay time model based on Deep Neural Network

3.1 Briefly on Neural Net's History

The history of Artificial Neural Network started in the 1940's [188]. A neurophysiologist, Warren McCulloch, and a mathematician, Walter Pitts, proposed the first mechanistic model of a simple neural network using electrical circuits [189]. The components were binary devices firing after fixed thresholds of the signal have been reached, thus mimicking the brain's nerve cells (McCulloch–Pitts neuron). Together with Jerome Lettvin (a cognitive scientist), Norbert Wiener (a mathematician) and John von Neumann, they formed a group of the cyberneticians. Soon, von Neumann was the first to publish the concept of the modern computer [190], a stored-program binary computing machine (the EDVAC, now known as the von Neumann architecture). He suggested modeling the computer using Pitts and McCulloch's neural networks. Vacuum tubes were to imitate neurons. Von Neumann's experience with the predecessor of *his* computer (the ENIAC), was that reprogramming meant to reroute all the wires and switches taking eventually several weeks. The solution based on neural networks would result in *reprogramming neurons* in the case of wishing to perform a new function, which would be much faster. This indicated a new need - the computer would require a memory to store these settings.

In 1956 the Dartmouth Summer Research Project on Artificial Intelligence took place with several mathematicians and scientists, among others, Marvin Minsky, John McCarthy, Claude Shannon and Nathan Rochester of IBM. The now seminal event was the moment when the term *Artificial Intelligence* was coined and an era of discovery and tremendous optimism followed. The Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA, an agency of the United States Department of Defense) encouraged financially the AI field, making MIT, CMU (Carnegie Mellon University) and Stanford the leading institutions of AI research together with Edinburgh University. Japan completed the first humanoid robot, WABOT-1, able to walk, transport objects and communicate in Japanese. These were the golden years of Artificial Intelligence until 1970's. Due to lack of progress driven mainly by limited computer power and Minsky's criticism of Frank Rosenblatt's perceptron (the first real precursor to modern neural networks), DARPA cut off funding resulting in no research on neural networks for the next 10 years. However, Japan continued research, introducing in 1981 their Fifth Generation project (worth \$850 million). The UK and the US in order to not lag behind set up new programs. This coincided with the charismatic presentation of a paper by John Hopfield from CALTECH. Hopfield's idea was to create useful devices, not to model the brain and create artificial intelligence. He proposed a type of recurrent artificial neural network known as the Hopfield network [191]. He had proven to many that such networks could work. In 1986, David E. Rumelhart, Geoffrey E. Hinton and Ronald J. Williams in [192] described a new learning procedure, back-propagation, for multilayer neural networks. Multilayer networks were able to learn nonlinear functions and, actually, any function.

Progress in artificial neural networks would not be possible without discoveries in the field of biology. Joseph Erlanger and Herbert Spencer Gasser identified several varieties of nerve fiber and formulated the relationship between action potential velocity and fiber diameter, which brought them jointly the Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine in 1944. Donald Hebb (a neurophysiologist) pointed out that a synapse between two neurons strengthen when the neurons on either side of the synapse (input and output) have highly correlated outputs (Hebbian theory). Thereby pathways in the brain are formed and reinforced through repetition - brain neurons adapt during the learning process. It is briefly summarized as "*neurons wire together if they fire together*" [193]. In the artificial system it means that the connection weight increases if two neurons are highly correlated.

Then, there was one of the most cited papers, *What the Frog's Eye Tells the Frog's Brain* [194] by Lettvin, Maturana, McCulloch and Pitts. They analyzed the activity of single fibers in the optic nerve of a frog by opening up the frog's skull and attaching electrodes to single fibers in the optic nerves. The question they wanted to answer was what kind of stimulus causes the largest activity in one nerve. To their biggest surprise the output from the retina of the frog was independent of the light intensity but was very sensitive to the pattern of the image. Actually, they found four types of fibers, each with its own task in processing the picture in terms of: local contrast (sharp edges), the curvature of the edge of a dark object, movement of edges and shadows produced by movement. The eye came down to being a system of detection of an accessible bug, *a bug perceiver*. "*The eye speaks to the brain in a language already highly organized and interpreted, instead of transmitting some more or less accurate copy of the distribution of light on the receptors*", as they wrote in their paper [194].

3.2 Deep Neural Network

The deep neural network (DNN) is the artificial neural network (ANN) with many hidden layers. The ANN consists of layers of neurons, where the first layer is called the input layer and the last layer is called the output layer. The layers between input and output are called the hidden layers. Input nodes are passive which means that they duplicate the received input value and pass it to each node in the next layer. The connections between nodes contain parameters known as weights, which indicate the influence of a given node on the final output value. Nodes in hidden and output layers hold activation function. These nodes are active. The sum of input values multiplied by specific weights is passed to the active node's activation function. Additional nodes added to the layers are called bias nodes. These bias nodes hold constant values and support achieving better-fitted results of prediction by shifting the activation function characteristics.

Each iteration of the neural network training process consists of two steps: forward and backward propagation. Forward propagation is a simple forward pass of input values through all the neurons, which outputs a result called a prediction value. The backward propagation method is a part of the artificial neural networks supervised machine learning algorithm and it minimizes the neural network error, called the cost function, in each

iteration by adjusting the weights in all nodes. The value of the error is the difference between the predicted value obtained in the forward pass and the actual output value taken from the training set. After the training, when the error is small enough, only the forward propagation is used to obtain predictions. The biggest advantage of DNNs is high predictive power and flexibility of application.

Since 2006 *Deep Learning* is going through a renewed interest. The key factors in this revolution [195] are: parallel computing with GPUs (graphics processing units), appearance of large labeled datasets, backprop-friendly activation functions, software platforms, robust optimizers, etc. DNN is widely used in numerous aspects of life, for instance: self-driving cars, handwriting recognition, anti-spam filtering, web searches and rating systems. Now it is becoming more popular in science as well.

3.3 Ignition Delay Time Model

The objective of this study is to introduce an ignition delay time model based on Deep Learning, as according to the Author's best knowledge IDTs have not been yet modeled with a deep neural network. The model will be created for C1–C4 hydrocarbons for detonation relevant conditions utilizing the dataset of experimental IDTs collected for DRMs' assessment purpose in the previous chapter. The dataset consists of IDTs shorter than 1 ms and after exclusion of poorer quality data. Hence, 2139 points are considered (1578 for argon, 561 for nitrogen), with this amount of points sufficient for deployment of the deep neural network. It was decided to develop two separate models - the first for mixtures diluted with argon, the second for nitrogen diluted.

3.3.1 Model

The models were built with deep feedforward networks (multilayer perceptrons, MLP), which are the quintessential deep learning models [196]. The FCNN4R 0.6.2 package [197] for R was utilized for the model development. The models have 8 inputs: fuel type, temperature [K], inverse temperature [1000/K], pressure [bar], equivalence ratio, fuel molar fraction, oxygen molar fraction and dilution molar fraction. The output of the models is the natural logarithm of ignition delay time [$\ln(\mu s)$], as the experimental values

varied from 2.6 up to 1000 μs and their distribution was skewed (Figure 3.1). Both sets of IDTs were divided into train and test sets in a proportion of 80:20. The detailed structure of the networks was a result of hyperparameter tuning within the following ranges:

- the number of hidden layers: 1–5
- the number of nodes: 5–15
- the L^2 regularization parameter [198]: 10^{-3} , 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-6} , 10^{-7} .

The activation function in all nodes was the symmetric sigmoid function (hyperbolic tangent).

Figure 3.1. Comparison of histograms of IDT and natural logarithm of IDT. The second picture shows a histogram, which is less skewed, which is advantageous for modeling purposes.

To prevent the model from the overfitting a 5-fold cross validation was used on each combination of the hyperparameters. The resilient backpropagation (Rprop) algorithm was used for optimization of the networks. The optimal hyperparameters were: for nitrogen data set: 3 hidden layers with 15 nodes each, for argon data set: 2 hidden layers with 15 nodes each. The deep neural network structure for argon is presented in Figure 3.2. The L^2 regularization coefficient was 10^{-5} in both cases. Additionally, in order to handle relatively small datasets the deep networks were trained 200 times, each time on a different randomized training set. The models having the lowest Mean Absolute Errors on test sets became the final models. The approach of model construction, tuning and training is similar to the one utilized by Malik et al. in [199] devoted to development of a detonation cell size model.

Figure 3.2. Deep neural network structure used in the present study

3.3.2 Results

The performance of the DNN models is measured by Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) and the Pearson coefficient (CORR). In Figure 3.3 the DNN performance on a test set for both nitrogen and argon diluted mixtures is presented and compared to two well-performing DRMs: NUIG n-Heptane [143] and Polimi PRF PAH LT [147–150]. In the left column of Figure 3.3 experimental uncertainty range (assumed as $IDT \pm 20\%$) is marked by the yellow area. Predictions belonging to the *area* are considered as a perfect match to experiment. In the right part of Figure 3.3 experimental uncertainty is taken into account while calculating CORR. The DNN models' Pearson correlation coefficient with experimental uncertainties taken into consideration has a very high value of 97.8%, which is higher than both DRMs. NUIG n-Heptane has a good tendency and the scatter of points is symmetrical, whereas the Polimi mechanism has a general tendency to underestimate IDTs.

Figure 3.3. Predicted IDT vs. experimental IDT for both argon and nitrogen diluted mixtures. Comparison of DNN model to NUIG n-Heptane and Polimi PRF PAH LT (DNN performance shown on a test set; 400 randomly selected points are shown for DRMs). Left: Experimental uncertainty is marked by the yellow area. Right: Experimental uncertainty is taken into account in CORR and MAE calculations.

In Tables 3.1–3.3 MAE and MAPE are compared without distinction between inert gases, for argon only and for nitrogen only, respectively. In all cases the DNN models have the highest accuracy and performance. It can be seen that both the DNN model and DRMs have better performance for nitrogen points. It might be concluded that the scatter of experimental points in case of argon is higher.

Table 3.1. Performance comparison of DNN model and DRMs for both argon and nitrogen diluted mixtures.

	NUIG n-Heptane	Polimi PRF PAH LT	DNN
<i>no experimental uncertainties</i>			
MAE	78,2	112,2	54,5
MAPE	23,7%	37,6%	20,3%
<i>experimental uncertainties, IDT \pm 20%</i>			
MAE	34,3	57,8	16,1
MAPE	9,9%	19,9%	7,2%

Table 3.2. Performance of DNN model and DRMs for argon diluted mixtures only.

	NUIG n-Heptane	Polimi PRF PAH LT	DNN Argon
<i>no experimental uncertainties</i>			
MAE	82,8	111,4	60,8
MAPE	25,0%	39,2%	23,7%
<i>experimental uncertainties, IDT \pm 20%</i>			
MAE	39,2	59,4	21,3
MAPE	10,8%	21,5%	9,6%

Table 3.3. Performance of DNN model and DRMs for nitrogen diluted mixtures only.

	NUIG n-Heptane	Polimi PRF PAH LT	DNN Nitrogen
<i>no experimental uncertainties</i>			
MAE	67,7	115,3	38,6
MAPE	20,7%	33,0%	11,6%
<i>experimental uncertainties, IDT \pm 20%</i>			
MAE	23,2	53,8	2,7
MAPE	7,9%	15,5%	1,3%

In Table 3.4 accuracy of the DNN models, NUIG n-Heptane and Polimi PRF PAH LT is presented for individual hydrocarbons. Presented MAE and MAPE have included experimental uncertainty of IDT measurements. In the majority (7 of 11) of hydrocarbons the DNN models have the lowest errors (namely: methane, ethene, propane, 2-butene, iso-butene, iso-butane, n-butane). MAPE varies from 0.0 up to 8.3% for these species.

In the case of propene MAPE of 7.1% indicates very good performance. The poorest predictability of the DNN models is for acetylene, ethane and 1-butene. MAPE is in the range from 14.9% up to 17.2%. NUIG’s accuracy for 1-butene is also higher than 10%.

Table 3.4. Performance of DNN model and DRMs for individual hydrocarbons. Calculations of MAE and MAPE took into account experimental uncertainties.

	NUIG n-Heptane		Polimi		DNN	
	MAE	MAPE	MAE	MAPE	MAE	MAPE
CH₄	64,0	15,9%	61,0	18,8%	12,5	5,8%
C₂H₂	8,0	2,5%	23,9	14,3%	22,0	15,8%
C₂H₄	66,5	17,6%	65,9	20,8%	31,5	8,3%
C₂H₆	19,0	7,1%	59,9	18,7%	49,0	17,2%
C₃H₆	10,2	3,7%	83,4	21,8%	22,5	7,1%
C₃H₈	57,5	17,1%	64,5	24,0%	10,2	5,0%
1-C₄H₈	50,2	10,6%	48,0	14,1%	60,1	14,9%
2-C₄H₈	27,9	8,2%	98,5	34,7%	0,0	0,0%
iso-C₄H₈	29,2	7,6%	66,9	17,3%	30,3	6,3%
iso-C₄H₁₀	30,6	8,1%	71,5	24,8%	5,5	2,4%
n-C₄H₁₀	28,0	8,9%	107,8	32,4%	8,6	3,7%

3.3.3 Conclusion

The DNN models for IDT of C1–C4 hydrocarbon mixtures have been developed using the experimental dataset collected in Chapter 2. The models have comparable performance to the *best* DRM (NUIG n-Heptane) and much shorter computational time (DNN: less than 1 ms, NUIG n-Heptane: ~2 min). Hence, the use of DNN models is a reasonable choice for CFD simulations of DDT. Nevertheless, one needs to keep in mind that the models are valid only within the ranges they have been trained. Therefore, for conditions which differ strongly from the training set it is recommended to validate the approach with DRMs. The models can be easily extended to new experimental data as published.

Chapter 4

Summary and conclusions

Ignition delay time of a mixture depends on the composition of the mixture (fuel type; fractions of fuel, oxidizer and inert gas) and thermodynamic conditions (temperature, pressure, heat loss). This is a key physical property controlling the transition to detonation and the propagation of detonation. Despite the mechanisms of transition to detonation, the detonation wave is formed when the reaction wave and the leading shock wave couple and by the same token when the ignition delay time behind the shock wave is short enough. Ignition delay times are calculated with use of dedicated detailed reaction mechanisms.

A quantitative theory of three-dimensional detonations has not been yet developed, therefore researcher and engineers use experimental parameters to describe and categorize the dynamics of the detonation. These experimental parameters include detonation cell size, critical initiation energy, critical tube diameter, etc. The need of detonability estimation led to the formulation of correlations between these parameters and the ones which can be computed from ZND theory: ignition delay time behind the leading shock wave, induction zone length, and reaction zone width. Nevertheless, these calculated parameters strongly differ depending on the mechanism used. Wrongly calculated induction zone lengths lead to incorrect values of detonation cell width, etc. Hence, selection of the appropriate chemical reaction mechanism is crucial due to safety reasons.

In order to enable more reliable numerical investigations of transition to detonation the analysis of detailed reaction mechanisms' performance in the reproduction of ignition

delay times was carried out. The analysis was devoted to C1–C4 hydrocarbons, as they form a group of globally used fuels and, moreover, their chemistry is important for non-aromatic species at high temperatures. An extensive literature review was completed in search of ignition delay times from shock tube experiments as they most closely represent the conditions appearing in detonation. The review highlighted gaps in IDT data: some hydrocarbons are more well understood, while others have little information provided. The observations may be useful for future experimental research. Due to the general sparsity of data, the analysis of mechanisms' accuracy was valid in some regions only. The accumulated IDTs were simulated with fifteen well established kinetic mechanisms and then the mechanisms' performance were compared. The Author presented the comparison at different levels of generality, providing guidance as to which mechanism performs best across all investigated conditions, which differed strongly between mixtures. Additionally, ignition delay time models based on a Deep Neural Network were proposed. The DNN models have a very high accuracy, comparable with the best mechanisms. And most importantly, IDTs' computations using the DNN models are incomparably shorter than with the mechanisms. The developed models might be a reasonable choice for CFD simulations of the DDT.

In the course of summarizing the conducted work and writing this dissertation important future tasks have come to the mind of the Author. Firstly, it would be beneficial to extend the analysis of detailed reaction mechanisms for the Curve Matching method or at least for directly testing activation energy reproduction. Activation energy is a stability parameter and technically it is the slope of the natural logarithm of ignition delay time against inverse temperature. Activation energy controls stability and regularity of detonation cell structure, hence controlling propensity of a mixture to undergo the DDT. These task could be done based on experimental data already collected for this dissertation. Secondly, mechanisms' accuracy for reproduction of laminar burning velocities and species' concentration profiles could be conducted, in order to make up more comprehensive study of reaction mechanisms. Sensitivity analyses with respect to reaction rate constants could help to optimize the mechanisms in the future. Thirdly, the work could be extended to other fuels and ignition delay times at lower temperatures e.g. from rapid compression machines. Thereby, conditions relevant to piston engines and knocking combustion would be addressed, which make up an extremely interesting research field.

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